

D3.4

Final evaluation and summary of training programs

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
CC	Creative Commons Attribution license
DMP	Data Management Plan
D	Document (data raw material)
DoA	Description of Action
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IP	Interview Person
MAXQDA	Qualitative data analysis software
PBL	Problem-Based Learning
RDM	Research Data Management
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SAGER	Sex and Gender Equity in Research
SPARC	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition
T3.3	Task 3.3
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive Summary

This report presents the final, summative evaluation of the training programmes implemented within the PATTERN project, which aims to develop and implement high-quality trainings in open and responsible research and innovation (RRI) across Europe. The project focuses on widening participation and fostering transferable skills within the European Research Area across eight thematic areas, including FAIR data management, Open Access, Citizen Science, and Management and Leadership.

This report covers the second and final learning cycle of pilot implementation (May 2025 to April 2026) and additionally presents data from the first learning cycle that could not be included in the earlier evaluation report (D3.3). It thus provides a comprehensive account of the scope of PATTERN training activity, assessing learning outcomes, individual changes, and institutional impact across both cycles. The evaluation addresses three levels of assessment — the trainings, the participants, and the institutions — drawing on a mixed-methods design that included quantitative participant questionnaires (1,747 responses across 116 trainings), qualitative analysis of participant and facilitator feedback, and semi-structured interviews with representatives from 10 institutions.

Overall, participant satisfaction was high: the majority of participants found the trainings well organised, relevant, and worthwhile, and reported increased interest in the subject matter. Qualitative findings confirm and deepen this picture: interactivity, peer discussion, and practical application were the most universally valued features across all thematic areas and participant groups. Participants most commonly described their primary gain as new knowledge and raised awareness rather than fully consolidated skills, a finding that reflects the inherent format constraints of single-session trainings rather than a shortcoming of content quality, and one that points to the value of sustained follow-up mechanisms. Interviews with institutional representatives confirm that the PATTERN trainings are highly effective in translating abstract Open Science and RRI frameworks into concrete, institutionally relevant practice, and describe them as strategically significant instruments for institutional positioning and capacity-building.

Based on these findings, the report concludes with recommendations for three audiences:

For trainers and facilitators: prioritise interactive, hands-on formats over passive lectures, making time for practical exercises; clearly separate awareness-raising from skill development, framing single sessions as introductions and, where possible, designing follow-up activities such as peer learning or advanced workshops to foster lasting skills; and tailor content and teaching methods to different participant groups, especially bachelor's students, natural scientists, and professionals such as librarians, while considering which pedagogical methods and digital tools fit which context and group best.

For future training developers and programme designers: focus on topics with clear, immediate relevance to researchers' daily work, making the scope of broader topics explicit to avoid mismatched expectations; design training materials to be

modular and self-contained, accompanied by clear guides for adaptation to different disciplines and institutional settings, to support long-term reuse; and remove institutional barriers to Open RRI training by offering incentives like credits or certification and aligning training contents with institutional mandates.

For Open RRI funders and policymakers: go beyond addressing individual researchers towards facilitating institutional change, using policy levers such as mandatory requirements (e.g. Data Management Plans, Gender Equality Plans) to drive demand for training; reward adaptable, well-documented, and openly licensed materials in evaluation criteria for future projects, rather than participant numbers alone; and ensure new funding calls address emerging issues that current modules miss, notably artificial intelligence's impact on research integrity and authorship, and the need to build lasting communities around Open RRI.

2 Introduction

This report – Deliverable 3.4 – presents the final evaluation of the training programmes implemented in the PATTERN project. It covers the second and final learning cycle of pilot implementation, which ran from May 2025 to April 2026. Where data from the first learning cycle could not be included in the earlier evaluation report (D3.3) due to timing, we also present it here. The deliverable focusses on analysing the learning outcomes, individual changes, institutional impact, and lessons learned and future potential of the PATTERN trainings for improving researchers' transferable skills across eight thematic areas.

The goal of this report is to provide a comprehensive and evidence-based account of whether and how the PATTERN trainings achieved their aims. We assess what participants gained from the trainings, how their experiences varied across different groups and contexts, and what barriers and success factors shaped implementation both from the training participants' and the training facilitators' point of views. We also examine whether the trainings produced any lasting changes at the institutional level, and we identify practical lessons for future projects, training providers, and policymakers who wish to support open and responsible research and innovation or upscale the PATTERN methodology.

The evaluation follows a mixed-methods approach to capture multi-dimensional perspectives from several actors involved in the trainings. The ZSI team developed several qualitative and quantitative evaluation instruments based on conceptual criteria drawn from previous research and participatory activities. These evaluation instruments included a training monitoring sheet to document each training's characteristics, a short quantitative participant questionnaire, an interactive evaluation activity, an extended participant questionnaire that combined the short questionnaire with open-ended questions, a template for facilitator reflection and documentation, and qualitative interviews with programme chairs, training facilitators, and coordinators.

This report is structured as follows. Section 3 briefly summarises the conceptual evaluation framework that guided our work. Section 4 describes the evaluation methodology, including changes we made after the first learning cycle. Section 5 presents the results, covering an overview of the trainings, findings from the participant questionnaire, the evaluation activity and extended questionnaire, facilitators' reflections, and the interviews. Section 6 provides a summary and section 7 presents conclusions and recommendations for three key target groups. The appendices contain all questionnaires, guidelines, and templates used in the evaluation as well as more detailed statistical results.

3 Conceptual Background: The Evaluation Framework

The evaluation of PATTERN trainings was informed by a conceptual evaluation framework which derived key evaluation criteria from a) existing literature and research on evaluation in higher education; and b) from activities and participatory workshops conducted as part of PATTERN. This evaluation framework formed the basis for developing the evaluation methodology and guides the interpretation of findings. The development and foundation of this framework was already described in D3.3 (Koller & Marschalek, 2025), which also includes additional details on sub-criteria. We summarise the final, consolidated framework here and refer the reader to D3.3 for further details.

The evaluation of PATTERN trainings followed a multi-level and multi-dimensional approach (see Figure 1). Multiple **levels of assessment** are considered in the evaluation, targeting the level of the training, of the participant, and of the institution. On the level of the training, we assessed its content, its appropriateness for its audience, and communication as well as presentation of materials. On the level of training participants, we evaluated their general perceptions of the training (e.g., was the training useful or interesting), self-perceived learning outcomes, and potential for practical implementation. On the level of the institution, we defined the sustainability of trainings resources, institutional and societal benefits, and lessons learned of involved actors (e.g., facilitators, program coordinators) as main evaluation criteria.

In the first round of evaluation reported in D3.3, we only assessed the level of trainings and the level of participants; in this final evaluation report, we also covered the institutional level to obtain a comprehensive picture of PATTERN's impact, potential limitations, and future avenues.

In addition to determining these three levels of evaluation, we also took **multiple dimensions of comparison** into account. Defining these dimensions allows examining how any reported and identified impacts may differ depending on participants' disciplines, career stages, and gender or a training's thematic area or format.

Information about these dimensions were primarily collected through the training monitoring sheet. PATTERN partners completed information about Thematic Area and Format using pre-defined drop-down lists, while discipline and career stage could be filled in as open fields and were standardised by the ZSI team. Perceptions of participant gender distributions were also indicated by PATTERN partners, but to avoid misgendering or binarizing participants, we decided to consider gender only in the participant questionnaire, where participants were able to self-identify.

Figure 1: Conceptual Evaluation Framework

4 Evaluation Methods and Process

The evaluation methodology follows a mixed-methods approach, whereby the ZSI team developed several qualitative and quantitative evaluation instruments following the criteria outlined in the conceptual evaluation framework. The pilot partners chose the appropriate instruments according to the ZSI's guidance and were responsible for data collection.

In this section, we describe the evaluation methods for assessing the different levels, the evaluation instruments, and how the data collected with each instrument was analysed.

All materials were provided in English. For partners who wished to translate the evaluation materials into their local language, ZSI provided a guideline explaining methods and best practices (see Appendix F).

4.1 Changes and updates compared to the first learning cycle

Following the learnings and feedback from evaluation in the first learning cycle, the evaluation methodology was revised and extended to a) adapt to project partners' needs and b) achieve a more comprehensive evaluation which also assesses the institutional level.

Firstly, the evaluation instruments for participants and facilitators were updated. The facilitator template for documentation and reflection was revised by removing redundancies, adding questions focusing on the PATTERN platforms, and asking about the involvement of external organisations. The participant evaluation was revised by adding an additional option: an extended questionnaire that combines both questions from the short questionnaire and the interactive evaluation activity used in Learning Cycle 1. Thus, depending on their preferences and the requirements of the participant groups, partners could choose to use the extended participant questionnaire only, use either the short participant questionnaire or the interactive evaluation activity, or both.

The second key update follows the description of T3.3 in the grant agreement, which foresaw conducting qualitative interviews with programme chairs. This process is described below.

4.2 Training monitoring sheet

ZSI developed a monitoring sheet to document the implementation of each training and its characteristics, provided to partners on the PATTERN SharePoint. The sheet collects information on each training such as the target group, format, and responsible institution. This information is used to characterise each training according to the dimensions defined in the consolidated framework of evaluation criteria. Project partners implementing pilots were responsible for populating the training monitoring sheet. The training monitoring sheet collected the following information:

- Training ID number for cross-referencing

- Name of the training
- Responsible institution
- Institution's country
- Date
- Level of the training (i.e., beginner, advanced, ...)
- Career stage of participants
- Discipline of participants
- Number of participants who attended
- Number of participants who registered, in case there was a large divergence
- Gender composition, only to complete if few participants completed the questionnaire and were able to self-identify their gender
- Training format (i.e., in person, online, hybrid, asynchronous)
- Specific information about the training format
- Number of training sessions
- Average length of each training
- Use of the PATTERN platforms OpenPlato and Projects
- Which evaluation instruments were used

4.3 Short Quantitative Participant Questionnaire

An online participant questionnaire was developed to assess criteria related to the **level of the training** (training content, appropriateness for the target group, presentation and communication) and **participants' general perceptions** were assessed using an online quantitative questionnaire. The quantitative questionnaire was used as a standardised evaluation instrument across different trainings, allowing for comparisons. The questionnaire was developed based on existing items used in previous research (Griffin et al., 2003; Kember & Leung, 2009; Rodgers et al., 2018; Visser-Wijnveen et al., 2016; Wilson et al., 1997). The questionnaire was designed to be short and resource-efficient while covering the most relevant aspects of the evaluation criteria (see Appendix A).

The questionnaire was developed and provided by the ZSI team and set up in questionnaire software. For project partners, collecting data with the questionnaire included the following steps:

- The questionnaire was set up in a Microsoft Office Form, which can be duplicated and used by anyone with a Microsoft account. A link to a tutorial was provided.¹
- Training facilitators or pilot partners duplicated the Form and independently distributed it among their training participants.
- For ZSI's analysis, it is vital to connect participants' responses collected with the questionnaire and the specific training the participants were in. Thus, partners were asked to include training name and date in the title of the forms as well as to refer to the link or title in the training monitoring sheet.
- After the data collection was completed, training facilitator or pilot partners shared the data with ZSI.

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pYWkWkxaxtM>

4.4 Interactive Evaluation Activity

For further assessing the **level of the participants**, we developed an **interactive evaluation activity** covering participants' learning outcomes and practical implementation of training contents. The ZSI team provided detailed guidelines on how to conduct the activity, along with the necessary materials (see Appendix C). Project partners were instructed to implement the activity during the final session of their training.

The evaluation activity prompted participants to add post-its along a rating scale from 0 (fully disagree) to 10 (fully agree) and to comment on the post-its, explaining their ratings and expressing their perspectives. Participants were prompted with these four questions:

- I enjoyed the training – because of ...
- The training was useful for me – and why ...
- I could gain new skills – and which ...
- I will apply what I have learned in practice – what in specific ...

The activity was designed to encourage exchange between participants and among participants and facilitators, allowing a more collective, dynamic and interactive evaluation experience. Thus, this activity also required moderation by training facilitators yet allowed facilitators to follow-up on participants' inputs in case of unclarities.

The activity could be conducted using either digital or analogue methods. ZSI created a Miro board template with multiple copies of the activity, enabling pilot partners to use it without a paid subscription. This facilitated ZSI's management of the data, supported facilitators, and simplified archival of the boards. For partners preferring a separate online board, a separate template link was provided. For analogue implementation, partners could either print a high-quality template mirroring the online board but adapted for offline use or recreate the activity using flipcharts.

To ensure all data was accessible to ZSI, partners were asked to document results using the designated reflection and documentation template outlined in the next section. Partners were also asked to translate non-English content or transcribe hand-written inputs.

For self-paced or asynchronous courses, we recommended embedding the Miro board within the course website (e.g., OpenPlato), possibly as a separate module. This provided a degree of interactivity for asynchronous participants, allowing them to view others' contributions, add their own insights, and make connections. While this differs from live training, it offers a complementary feedback mechanism alongside the anonymous, individual feedback questionnaire.

All materials received were imported into the qualitative analysis software MaxQDA and coded. Miro boards were exported as PDFs, which allowed to code the text on participants' post-its, while transcripts of analogue implementations and translations provided by pilot partners were imported as Microsoft Word documents.

4.5 Extended Participant Questionnaire

The extended version of the participant questionnaire combines both the short questionnaire and the interactive evaluation activity in one instrument by appending the questions from the evaluation activity to the original participant questionnaire. This resulted in one instrument completed individually by each participant, removing the collaborative and collective elements that were a core element of the evaluation activity. In turn, it allowed to streamline distribution and data collection. Similar to the short questionnaire, it was set up in Microsoft Forms.

For analysis, the closed-ended questions were merged and analysed together with the data from the short participant questionnaire. The questions incorporated from the interactive evaluation activity were merged and analysed together with the data from the interactive evaluation activity in MAXQDA. Questionnaire responses not in English were translated using Claude AI.

4.6 Template for Reflection and Documentation

This template was completed by training facilitators for two main purposes: documenting the training and evaluation activities and reflecting on the training from the facilitators' perspective (see Appendix D). The template offers space for describing the activities and uploading photos and screenshots of participants' distributions. Further, training facilitators were encouraged to provide their reflections and describe their experiences of implementing the training, including reflections on the training approach and used materials, challenges and uncertainties, things that went well, and recommendations. These reflections additionally informed the analysis, complemented the assessment of evaluation criteria, and provided valuable insights for future training implementations.

4.7 Qualitative interviews with programme chairs, training facilitators, and coordinators

We conducted qualitative semi-structured interviews with representatives from 10 PATTERN institutions to gain a higher-level perspective on training evaluation and collect evidence for an institutional-level assessment. Following the description of T3.3 in the PATTERN grant agreement, we asked the PATTERN coordinating partner for suggestions of interviewees fitting the role of programme chairs and training facilitators, whereby we also included training coordinators. We invited all suggested potential interviewees, out of which two were not available. Thus, we did not interview all partners involved in implementing PATTERN trainings, and we chose not to interview the work package leader to avoid potential conflicts of interest.

The interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams between November 2025 and January 2026, with two ZSI team members acting as interviewers. Each interview took between 40 and 60 minutes. The interviews were structured following a pre-defined interview guideline, informed by the evaluation framework (see Appendix E). The interview recordings were automatically transcribed by Teams and checked afterwards by a ZSI team member. The transcripts were imported into MAXQDA and all interviews were coded by both ZSI interviewers.

The interview partners represented a range of positions within their organisations and the PATTERN project. Within their home institutions, three worked as data experts, three held strategic, management or policy roles, and five were involved in teaching and training delivery. When describing their project roles, most participants focused on their involvement in training activities, while four mentioned management responsibilities and two identified themselves as core project members within their institutions.

Rather than organising the interview findings according to these self-described roles, which often overlapped and would complicate analysis of the two joint interviews where two colleagues discussed shared experiences, we structured our analysis following the categories set out in the PATTERN Description of Action (DoA). *Thematic leaders* developed training modules and content while also testing trainings, whereas *pilot organisations* implemented trainings with target groups without being involved in content development. We interviewed representatives from four pilot organisations and six thematic leaders who also piloted trainings. Table 1 provides an overview of the roles of interview partners' organisations in PATTERN and the code we use to reference them in the description of results, guaranteeing anonymity.

Code	Role of organisation in PATTERN (according to DoA)
IP1	Thematic Leader & Pilot Organisation
IP2	Pilot Organisation
IP3	Thematic Leader & Pilot Organisation
IP4	Thematic Leader & Pilot Organisation (through network)
IP5	Pilot Organisation
IP6	Thematic Leader & Pilot Organisation
IP7	Pilot Organisation
IP8	Thematic Leader & Pilot Organisation
IP9	Pilot Organisation
IP10	Thematic Leader & Pilot Organisation

Table 1: Roles of interview partners in PATTERN.

4.8 Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative data analysed in this report included the training monitoring sheet data and the standardised quantitative data collected through participant questionnaires (both the extended and the short version were analysed as one dataset).

Data from the training monitoring sheet was analysed using descriptive statistics and frequencies. Questionnaire data was analysed using descriptive exploration of response frequencies as well as visual depiction of means and standard deviations for group comparisons. To assess whether any descriptive differences were also

meaningful, we conducted ANOVAs (ANalysis Of Variance), a statistical technique to assess whether any group differences are statistically significant and different from zero, and post-hoc tests to ascertain the specific groups that differ. In the main text, we only report statistically significant results in a narrative manner, while reporting exact statistical figures in a visual manner in Appendix G.

To gain a deeper understanding of how participants' training experience, we used a statistical method called psychometric network analysis (Borsboom et al., 2021; Dalege et al., 2017). Instead of looking at each survey question in isolation, this approach treats all questions as part of an interconnected system of attitudes, in this case, of attitudes towards the training experience. The key advantage is that we can see the unique relationship between any two questions while accounting for the influence of all the others as well as for training characteristics. Using this method allowed us to assess how coherent the overall network is, whether any groupings of survey items emerge, which evaluation aspects mattered the most or drove participants' overall impressions of their training experience, or look into the role of certain training characteristics. In network analysis, green lines usually represent positive particle correlations and red lines negative correlations between variables, whereby the thickness of the line indicates the strength of the correlation.

4.9 Qualitative Analysis

Qualitative data consisted of the qualitative evaluation activity (Miro board results, including qualitative questions from the extended participant questionnaire), facilitators' templates, and transcripts of qualitative interviews. All materials were imported into MaxQDA. Initial automated pre-coding was derived from the questions in the collected materials, providing a first organisational structure. Additional subcodes were manually added to capture emergent, in vitro codes, ensuring that novel or unexpected themes were incorporated.

For the qualitative participant data and facilitators' templates, the coded segments were subjected to a two-stage analytical process. First, Claude-AI was used to assist with preliminary thematic grouping, providing an overview of patterns and enabling rough categorisation of the data. In the second stage, a systematic qualitative content analysis was performed following Mayring's framework of qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2000). This involved iterative, rule-guided reduction of the coded segments into categories, abstraction and summarisation of content, and refinement of category definitions to maintain conceptual clarity. Both inductive and deductive coding principles were applied, allowing the analysis to capture predefined analytical interests as well as emergent themes across the dataset. The combined approach ensured a robust, transparent, and replicable interpretation of the qualitative material.

The qualitative interviews with partners were coded jointly by both authors of this report using qualitative content analysis with deductive and inductive coding (Mayring, 2000), including iterative checks between coders.

To ensure the protection of participants' privacy whilst maintaining the traceability of data for analytical purposes, all qualitative data sources were anonymised prior to analysis and assigned unique identifiers. Responses collected through the interactive evaluation activity and the extended participant questionnaire are referenced by

document number as assigned in the qualitative analysis software MAXQDA (e.g., D 1, D 2), reflecting the document-level structure of the imported data. Facilitator reflection templates are referenced by a sequential numeric identifier (e.g., 1, 2). Interview partners are referenced by a sequential code prefixed with "IP" (e.g., IP 1, IP 2). In all cases, the mapping between these identifiers and the corresponding individuals or institutions is maintained in a separate, access-restricted key file that is not available to readers of this report. This approach follows established principles of research data management and research integrity, ensuring that findings can be traced and verified internally whilst protecting the anonymity of all contributors.

5 Results

5.1 Overview of trainings

In this section, we present an overview of the trainings implemented within PATTERN, covering both Learning Cycle 2 and those from Learning Cycle 1 that could not be included in the previous evaluation deliverable (D3.3) due to timing constraints. Overall, 150 trainings were logged in the training monitoring sheet. Of these, 35 fell within Learning Cycle 1 (which ended in April 2025), while 115 were conducted in Learning Cycle 2, spanning May 2025 to April 2026 (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Overview of implemented trainings

We collected extensive evaluation data across all 150 trainings. Only 20 trainings (13.3%) were not evaluated at all, meaning neither facilitators nor participants provided feedback. The most common evaluation instrument was the facilitator template (110 trainings, 73%), followed by the extended participant questionnaire, which combined qualitative and quantitative elements, used in almost half of all trainings (72 trainings, 48%) and the short participant questionnaire used in 44 trainings (20%). The interactive evaluation activity was the least common, used in 19 trainings (13%) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Data collection across different evaluation instruments

We now describe the characteristics of these 150 trainings.

The PATTERN project defined eight thematic areas of transferable skills to be covered across its trainings. The most prevalent was FAIR data management, addressed in 48 trainings (32%). Open Access (26%), Management and Leadership (13%), and Citizen Science (11%) were also common. The remaining thematic areas were each addressed in 1% to 7% of trainings. One training spanned both FAIR data management and Open Access, and one also covered Open RRI more broadly (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Prevalence of PATTERN thematic areas

Training levels varied, though most trainings targeted beginners. Of all trainings, 43% targeted beginners only, while 44% targeted both beginner and intermediate levels (see Figure 5). Only four trainings addressed intermediate and advanced levels, covering thematic areas of Gender, Non-Discrimination and Inclusion in Research (three trainings) and Management and Leadership (one training).

Figure 5: Prevalence of training levels

In terms of format, most trainings were conducted live and in person (57%), with many also delivered as live online sessions such as webinars (39%). Hybrid and self-paced formats were rare (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Prevalence of training formats

The number of participants per training varied considerably, with a mean of 38.2 (SD = 39.18) and a median of 20. The minimum was 2 participants and the maximum 230 participants, with a range of 228. The number of sessions per training had a mean of 1.54 (SD = 1.06) and a median of 1, with a maximum of 6 sessions. Session length ranged from 0.75 to 7 hours, with a mean of 2.10 hours (SD = 0.98) and a median of 2 hours.

The PATTERN platforms Projects and OpenPlato were used across many trainings, each offering different pedagogical opportunities. Projects was slightly more common, used in 31% of trainings, compared to 29% for OpenPlato (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Use of the PATTERN platforms

Participants' disciplines were notably mixed across trainings (based on information provided by facilitators): 89% of trainings involved participants from multiple disciplines, while trainings with participants from a single discipline were rare (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Prevalence of training participants' disciplines

A similar picture emerged for participants' career backgrounds (see Figure 9). Almost a third of trainings involved mixed groups of participants in research positions (such as postdocs) and non-research positions (such as librarians). A quarter involved only researchers at PhD level or above. Some trainings (18%) included only PhD students, while 13% involved a mix of research-related participants, such as Master's students

and postdocs together. More information about participants' disciplines and career backgrounds will be described based on self-reported information in the section covering participant questionnaire results.

Figure 9: Prevalence of training participants' career backgrounds

5.2 Participant questionnaire

5.2.1 Sample characteristics and training statistics

Overall, 1,747 participants involved in 116 trainings completed either the short or extended version of the participant questionnaire. Response numbers per training varied considerably, ranging from 1 to 79, with a small number of trainings collecting no responses at all.

The sociodemographic data reveals a diverse sample, though with some dominant groups. Close to 70% of respondents identified as women (65%; n = 1139), 29% as men (n = 503), and 2% preferred not to indicate their gender (n = 32). Only seven participants identified as non-binary, while 66 respondents did not answer this question.

Regarding age, the sample ranged from 18 to 72, with a mean of 33.3 years (SD = 10.9) and a median of 29 years (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Overview of age distribution among questionnaire participants

Several disciplines were represented, though participants from the natural sciences made up the largest share at 39% (n = 676), followed by the social sciences at 16% (n = 284), and engineering and technology at 13% (n = 223). Other disciplines included medical and health sciences (8%; n = 147), arts and humanities (7%; n = 124), other disciplines (5%; n = 88), business and economics (3%; n = 61), library and information science (3%; n = 52), and law and legal sciences (1%; n = 10). Overall, 82 respondents did not answer this question.

By career stage, doctoral and predoctoral researchers formed the largest group at 34% (n = 594), followed by bachelor's students (20%; n = 358), master's students (11%; n = 195), senior scientists or professors (11%; n = 186), postdoctoral researchers (9%; n = 151), librarians or administrative staff (5% n = 87), and other (5%; n = 84). 92 respondents did not answer this question.

Almost half of all respondents attended a beginner and intermediate training (46%; n = 802), while 39% (n = 682) attended beginner-only trainings. Trainings covering all levels were attended by 5% of respondents (n = 89), while 2% of questionnaire participants were in intermediate (n = 42) or intermediate & advanced (n = 43) trainings, respectively. For 89 questionnaire participants, no data on training level was available.

The distribution across thematic areas was wide, though the largest share came from Open Access trainings (34%; n = 602), followed by FAIR data management (19%; 330), Citizen Science (16%; n = 282), and Science Communication (11%; n = 185); all other thematic areas accounted for less than 10% each, with 124 participants in Research Integrity, 136 participants in Management and Leadership, 60 participants in Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion, 20 participants in Dissemination and Exploitation, and 8 participants in a training that combined Open Access with FAIR data management.

Most participants attended a live, in-person training (62%; n = 1085), with about a third attending live, online trainings (37%; n = 652). Participants from hybrid (n = 1) or self-paced trainings (n = 9) were a very small minority.

Almost all participants had not yet encountered the OpenPlato platform at the time of completing the questionnaire (91%; n = 1590, according to information from training facilitators), though some may have done so afterwards, as OpenPlato is often used for archiving and as a repository. However, 35% (n = 607) attended trainings that used the Projects platform.

5.2.2 Overview of responses to each survey item

This section provides an overview of responses to each survey item, to examine how participants assessed different aspects of their training. Graphs of response frequencies for each item separately that also include sample sizes per item are provided in Appendix G.

The results tell a clear story: participants were overwhelmingly satisfied with their training experience. Across nearly every item, strong majorities somewhat agreed, agreed, or strongly agreed with positive statements, and disagreed with negative ones.

On the quality of training materials, 95.8% of participants found them clear, and 96% found them relevant and up to date. Responses were more mixed on the question of whether the training tried to cover too many topics: 45% disagreed or strongly disagreed, but 26.3% agreed or strongly agreed, suggesting that a notable minority felt that the scope of their training was too broad. Yet, 87% agreed that the training taught them a lot of new concepts, indicating that even those who felt the training was dense still learned a lot.

Participants also reported a manageable and well-organised learning experience. 92.6% agreed that they completed the training requirements without feeling unduly stressed, and 87.9% found it sufficiently flexible for their personal learning needs. The training's structure received particularly strong endorsement, with 96.5% agreeing it was well organised, and 93.7% agreeing they had sufficient opportunity to engage actively. On the corresponding negative item, 84.8% disagreed that the aims and objectives were unclear, reinforcing this positive picture.

Ratings for the online platforms used were also high, with 90.3% finding them adequate for learning, though the survey question did not specify the platform used. Engagement with the subject matter was strong as well: 86.3% agreed that the training increased their interest in the topic. Taken together, these results point to a training experience that was not only well delivered but also effective from a learning perspective, sparking curiosity among participants.

Overall satisfaction was correspondingly high. 93.6% of participants found their training worthwhile, and 94% were satisfied with its quality.

Figure 11 translates these results into a boxplot to summarise the response patterns. The box presents the middle 50% of responses, the bold line indicates the median, the whiskers (horizontal lines to the left and right of the box) the most extreme values within 1.5 times the interquartile range, and the dots represent individual data points,

allowing to better understand variation in responses. Furthermore, we present the means and standard deviations for each survey item in Figure 12, which also act as a reference point for the findings on group comparisons presented in the next section.

Figure 11: Boxplots for each questionnaire item. The x-axis represents the response options from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 7 (Strongly agree). Data points were jittered to increase legibility.

Figure 12: Means and standard deviations of each item. The x-axis represents the response options from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 7 (Strongly agree).

5.2.3 Comparisons across key groups and training characteristics

To further investigate and understand participants' training assessment, we also explored the extent to which different participant groups benefited from the trainings or how their experiences may have differed.

In the following sections, we report the results of statistical tests comparing the participant questionnaire data according to the key dimensions defined in the evaluation framework (see section 3): Discipline, Career Stage, Gender, Training Theme, and Training Format. Additionally, we explored whether the use of the PATTERN platforms Projects and OpenPlato in the training reveals different response patterns, based on information on platform use provided by the facilitators. Here, we describe the results only narratively, while graphs containing statistical results are provided in Appendix G.

5.2.3.1 Discipline

We found statistically significant group differences in nine of the 13 survey items, with means and standard deviations for each item across discipline groups shown in Figure 13.

A clear pattern emerged across these questionnaire items: participants from the natural sciences tended to rate the training less favourably than those from most other disciplines on nearly every dimension where differences were found. They found the training materials less clear than participants from all other disciplines except Law & Legal Sciences, Library & Information Sciences, and the „other disciplines” category. They also found the materials less relevant and up to date than participants from the medical and health sciences, though no significant differences emerged compared to the remaining groups.

Interestingly, natural science participants were also less likely to feel that the training covered too many topics, suggesting they were more comfortable with the broadness of content than participants from Engineering & Technology, Library & Information Sciences, Medical & Health Sciences, Social Sciences, and the „other disciplines” category. Despite this more positive view of scope, they agreed less that the training taught them many new concepts compared to most other groups, the exceptions being Arts & Humanities and Business & Economics, where no significant differences were found.

Beyond content, natural science participants also rated the training less favourably on several structural and experiential dimensions. They agreed less that the training provided sufficient flexibility for personal learning needs than participants from Engineering & Technology, Library & Information Sciences, Medical & Health Sciences, and Social Sciences. They also rated the training as less well-structured than participants from Medical & Health Sciences and the Social Sciences, and were less likely to report that the training increased their interest in the topic, with no significant differences found only for Arts & Humanities, Economics & Business, and Law & Legal Sciences.

This pattern extended to overall evaluations. Natural science participants were less likely to consider the training worthwhile than those from most other disciplines, the

exceptions being Library & Information Sciences and the „other disciplines” category. Similarly, they reported lower overall satisfaction with the quality of the training than all other groups, again except for Library & Information Sciences and „other disciplines.”

Four items showed no significant differences across discipline groups: managing the training requirements without undue stress, having the chance to actively engage, clarity of aims and objectives, and the adequacy of the online platforms as learning tools. In these respects, all participants responded similarly regardless of disciplinary background.

Figure 13: Overview of means and standard deviations across participants' disciplines.

5.2.3.2 Career Stage

We also assessed differences across career stages and found statistically significant differences in 10 of the 13 survey items (see Figure 14). The results reveal two broad patterns: bachelor's students were the most critical group, rating the training less favourably across most dimensions, while master's students and senior scientists/professors tended to give the most positive evaluations. Doctoral students and predoctoral researchers occupied a middle ground, rating several aspects of the training more positively than bachelor's students but less positively than more senior career stages.

Bachelor's students found the training materials less clear than librarians and administrative staff, master's students, postdoctoral researchers, and senior scientists/professors. They also found the materials less relevant and up to date than master's students, postdoctoral researchers, and senior scientists/professors. These gaps suggest that the training content may align less well with the expectations or prior knowledge of those at the beginning of their academic careers.

Opinions on whether the training covered too many topics provided a more nuanced picture. Bachelor's students were less likely than most other groups to feel the training was too broad, suggesting they were more comfortable with the scope. Master's students, by contrast, were more likely than doctoral students, senior scientists/professors, and librarians/administrative staff to feel the training covered too many topics.

Regarding learning outcomes, both bachelor's and doctoral students agreed less that the training taught them many new concepts compared to master's students, postdoctoral researchers, senior scientists/professors, and those in other career stages. Master's students, in turn, reported learning more new concepts than postdoctoral researchers. Together, these findings suggest that the training's content struck the right level of novelty most clearly for those in the middle and later stages of their careers.

Bachelor's students were less satisfied with the flexibility the training offered for personal learning needs than all other career stage groups. Doctoral students also agreed less on this point than librarians and administrative staff. Regarding structure, bachelor's students rated the training as less well organised than senior scientists/professors, while doctoral students found it less well-structured than both master's students and senior scientists/professors. A similar pattern appeared for the online platforms: bachelor's students rated them less favourably than master's students and senior scientists/professors, and doctoral students rated them less favourably than senior scientists/professors.

The career stage divide was most pronounced in participants' broader evaluations of the training. Bachelor's students were less likely than all other groups to report that the training increased their interest in the topic, while doctoral students also reported lower interest gains than librarians/administrative staff and master's students. When it came to perceiving the training as worthwhile, bachelor's students again rated it lower than all other groups, and doctoral students rated it lower than librarians/administrative staff, master's students, postdoctoral researchers, and senior scientists/professors.

Overall satisfaction followed the same pattern. Bachelor's students were less satisfied with the training quality than all other groups except doctoral students, and doctoral students were less satisfied than postdoctoral researchers and senior scientists/professors.

Three items showed no significant differences across career stages: managing the training requirements without undue stress, having the chance to actively engage, and clarity of aims and objectives. Whatever their career stage, participants responded similarly on these points, suggesting that the training delivered a consistent experience in these dimensions of training assessment.

Figure 14: Overview of means and standard deviations across participants' career stages.

5.2.3.3 Gender

We also compared training experiences across gender (see Figure 15). Statistically significant differences emerged only between those identifying as women and those identifying as men, which likely reflects the considerably smaller size of the non-binary and „prefer not to say” groups. We found a consistent pattern: where significant differences were found, women rated the training more favourably than men, though the differences were relatively small.

Women found the training materials clearer and more relevant and up to date than men and were more likely to agree that the training taught them many new concepts. These findings suggest that women found the content better adapted to their needs.

Women also rated the training as better structured and agreed more that it provided sufficient flexibility for their personal learning needs. In turn, men more often agreed that the aims and objectives of the training were not made clear, indicating slightly greater dissatisfaction on this aspect.

Women also rated the overall quality of the training higher than men and were more likely to consider the experience worthwhile.

Six items showed no significant gender differences: whether the training covered too many topics, managing requirements without undue stress, having the chance to actively engage, the adequacy of the online platforms, and whether interest in the topic increased. On these dimensions, men and women responded similarly.

Figure 15: Overview of means and standard deviations across participants' gender.

5.2.3.4 Training Theme

Comparing training experiences across PATTERN thematic areas produced the most complex pattern of results in this section because of the large numbers of groups (see Figure 16). Thus, in interpreting results, we focus on the highest and lowest-rated thematic areas for each dimension rather than detailing every significant difference. Effect sizes were mostly small throughout.

Overall, we found that FAIR data management, Open Access, and Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion consistently attracted the most positive ratings, while Research Integrity and Science Communication were often at the lower end, though all groups remained clearly positive overall.

This pattern may reflect how directly the different thematic areas speak to participants' immediate professional needs: topics such as FAIR data management and Open Access address concrete, practical requirements that researchers encounter regularly, also as part of standardised and institutionalised requirements. Similarly, gender inclusion has also become a standardised and institutional requirement in European framework programmes, which are crucial funding resources for many researchers. In contrast, topics like Science Communication may feel more peripheral to day-to-day work for many participants and are characterised by less structural integration. This interpretation is echoed in findings from the facilitators' perspectives discussed later in this report.

Participants in Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion and Open Access gave the highest ratings for clarity of training materials, with FAIR data management close behind. Research Integrity and Citizen Science gave the lowest ratings, though still from a position of general satisfaction. For relevance and currency of materials, FAIR data management came out on top, followed by Open Access, while participants in Science Communication and Research Integrity trainings rated these dimensions lowest.

Open Access and FAIR data management participants were most likely to feel the training covered too many topics, while Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion and Science Communication participants were least likely to feel this way. This suggests that the Open Access and FAIR data management trainings were perceived as particularly content-intense. Consistent with this, participants in FAIR data management and Open Access also reported the highest levels of new learnings, while those in Research Integrity and Science Communication reported the least.

FAIR data management participants provided highest ratings for structure, flexibility for personal learning needs, quality of online platforms for learning, and opportunities for active engagement. Ratings for Research Integrity and Science Communication were comparatively lower for structure, flexibility, and platform quality, while Citizen Science also rated the experience with digital platforms relatively worse.

The one exception to FAIR data management's ranking was active engagement, where Management and Leadership and Citizen Science scored highly. Open Access participants reported the fewest opportunities to engage actively despite rating most other dimensions positively.

We find similar tendencies for the overall evaluation questions. FAIR data management participants reported the greatest increase in interest, found the experience most worthwhile, and were most satisfied with the training quality. Open Access and Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion also performed strongly on these measures. Research Integrity and Science Communication were rated somewhat lower, though it is worth emphasising that even the lowest mean for overall satisfaction was 5.60 on a seven-point scale, which reflects a rather positive rating.

Two items showed no significant differences across thematic areas: managing the training requirements without undue stress, and clarity of aims and objectives. Regardless of the topic, participants experienced similar levels of pressure and similar clarity about what the training set out to achieve.

Figure 16: Overview of means and standard deviations across participants' training themes.

5.2.3.5 Training Format

For identifying statistically significant differences across training formats (see Figure 17), we focus on live in-person and live online trainings, as the number of participants in self-paced and hybrid formats was too small to draw reliable conclusions.

Overall, we found a clear pattern: online participants rated the training more favourably than in-person participants on almost every dimension, though the differences were small (but still statistically significant).

Online participants were more likely to find the training materials clear, relevant, and up to date. They also agreed more that the training taught them many new concepts and that it provided sufficient flexibility for their personal learning needs. Interestingly, they were also more likely to feel that the training tried to cover too many topics, suggesting that while online participants engaged more positively with the content overall, they were also more sensitive to its scope.

Online participants rated the training as better structured and found the online platforms more adequate as learning tools than in-person participants did. These differences may point to the fact that online participants dependent more on the digital infrastructure of the training than in-person participants. Another explanation lies in a self-selection pattern, whereby online participants intentionally chose online formats due to being more comfortable in online learning environments.

The one area where in-person participants showed more positive evaluations was active engagement: they reported more opportunities to participate during the training than online participants.

Regarding overall impressions, online participants were more likely to report that the training increased their interest in the topic, considered the overall experience worthwhile, and expressed higher satisfaction with the training's quality.

Two items showed no significant differences by format: managing the training requirements without undue stress, and clarity of aims and objectives. Regardless of how the training was delivered, participants responded similarly on these points.

Figure 17: Overview of means and standard deviations across participants' training format. Please note that no standard deviation could be calculated for Hybrid as it only consists of one person.

5.2.3.6 *PATTERN Platforms*

Finally, we compared training experiences based on whether the PATTERN platforms Projects or OpenPlato were used as part of the training (see Figure 18 and Figure 19). It is worth noting that this variable reflects the training facilitator's indication of platform use rather than whether participants consciously engaged with or rated the platform themselves.

Where statistically significant differences emerged for the Projects platform, they were relatively small in size. The overall pattern favours trainings that did not use Projects, with participants in those trainings rating most aspects of the experience more positively.

Participants whose training did not involve Projects found the materials clearer and more relevant and up to date, felt the training offered more flexibility for their personal learning needs, rated the online platforms as more adequate learning tools, were more likely to report increased interest in the topic, consider the overall experience worthwhile, and express higher overall satisfaction with the training quality.

In two dimensions, using Projects for the training was associated with a more positive outcome. One was active engagement: participants whose training involved Projects were more likely to report having had the chance to participate actively. This is consistent with Projects being a collaborative platform, and suggests it may contribute meaningfully to interactivity. The second dimension was that participants whose training did not involve Projects were more likely to feel the training covered too many topics.

Four items showed no significant differences based on Projects use: learning new concepts, managing requirements without undue stress, how well the training was structured, and clarity of aims and objectives.

Figure 18: Overview of means and standard deviations across the training's use of the Projects platform.

For OpenPlato, the pattern runs in the opposite direction to Projects: participants whose training involved OpenPlato rated their experience more positively across most dimensions, with small to medium effect sizes. This is a notable finding, though it should be interpreted with care given that only 149 participants reported OpenPlato use compared to over 1,000 who did not.

Participants whose training involved OpenPlato found the materials clearer, agreed more that the training taught them many new concepts, felt it offered sufficient flexibility for their personal learning needs, rated it as better structured, and were more likely to report having had the chance to actively engage. They also found the online platforms more adequate as learning tools, were more likely to report increased interest in the topic, and rated the overall experience as more worthwhile and of higher quality.

Participants without OpenPlato were more likely to feel the training covered too many topics and that its aims and objectives were not made clear.

These findings suggest that using OpenPlato could provide a clearer and more coherent structure and framing to the training, which may provide better orientation for content and learning objectives.

Two items showed no significant differences: whether the training materials were relevant and up to date, and managing the training requirements without undue stress.

Figure 19: Overview of means and standard deviations across the training's use of the OpenPlato platform.

5.2.4 Network Analysis

To complement the separate group comparisons above, we used network analysis to examine how the different aspects of training evaluation relate to one another, which aspects were most influential for participants' overall impressions, and whether any natural groupings of survey items emerge.

The network is presented in Figure 20. The survey items are strongly interconnected, with most associations running in the expected direction. Positive associations, shown in green, indicate that participants who responded favourably to one aspect of the training tended to do so across others as well: for instance, those who found the materials clear also tended to find them relevant and up to date. Negative associations, shown in red, appear largely between the negatively phrased items and the rest of the network. Participants who felt that aims and objectives were not made clear were less likely to report active engagement, clear and relevant materials, good structure, a worthwhile experience, or overall satisfaction.

Two associations stand out as particularly interesting. First, participants who felt the aims and objectives were not made clear were actually more likely to report completing the training without undue stress. This runs counter to expectations and may suggest that a lack of clear framing influences perceived quality of the training but does not necessarily increase pressure or workload. Second, participants who felt the training covered too many topics were more likely to indicate that they learned many new concepts and that their interest increased, but also more likely to feel that aims and objectives were unclear. This points to a tension between the scope of the

- 1: The training materials were clear.
- 2: The training materials were relevant and up to date.
- 3: It seemed to me that the training tried to cover too many topics.
- 4: The training taught me a lot of new concepts.
- 5: I managed to complete the requirements of the training without feeling unduly stressed.
- 6: The training provided sufficient flexibility for my personal learning needs.
- 7: The training was well structured.
- 8: I was given the chance to actively engage during the training.
- 9: The aims and objectives of this training were NOT made very clear.
- 10: The online platforms used in the training were adequate tools for learning.
- 11: During the training, my interest in the topic was increased.
- 12: Overall, the training experience was worthwhile.
- 13: Overall, I'm satisfied with the quality of this training.

Figure 20: Network of training evaluation.

content and the clarity of the purpose of this content: even though a broad scope may stimulate learning and interest, it risks being perceived as incoherent or without direction.

To assess the relative influence of each survey item within the network, we used a measure called strength, which captures how strongly a given item connects to all others. The two overall evaluation items, „Overall, I'm satisfied with the quality of this training” and „Overall, the training experience was worthwhile”, had the greatest influence on the network, which is consistent with their role as summary judgements that draw on all other aspects of the experience. With some distance behind them, the next most influential items were learning many new concepts, how well the training was structured, clarity of materials, and sufficient flexibility for personal learning needs. The least influential items were active engagement, adequacy of the online platforms, and the two negatively phrased items concerning aims and objectives and broadness of content.

Finally, we examined whether the survey items form natural groupings, that is, clusters of items that are more strongly related to each other than to the rest of the network, which may point to underlying dimensions of training quality that could be addressed in a targeted manner in future training design.

Three clusters emerged. The first and smallest consisted of the two negatively phrased items: whether the training covered too many topics and whether aims and objectives were not made clear.

The second cluster brought together the more general, evaluative items, in addition to new learnings: increased interest in the topic, the training experience being worthwhile, overall satisfaction with quality, and learning many new concepts. This cluster may represent a common, underlying judgement about whether the training was worth participants' time.

The third and largest cluster contained the remaining, more specific items covering materials, structure, flexibility, engagement, and platform quality. These reflect more concrete and distinct features of how the training was delivered and experienced.

In a second network analysis, we added training and participant characteristics to examine how these influence the network of training evaluations. Specifically, we included participants' age, the total number of attendees, the total number of training sessions, the length of training sessions, and whether the Projects or OpenPlato platforms were used (see Figure 21).

Before turning to the survey items, it is worth noting how the training characteristics themselves relate to each other within the network. OpenPlato tended to be used more in trainings with older participants, while Projects tended to be used less if participants were older. Trainings with more sessions were more likely to use Projects, and trainings with longer sessions also used Projects more often while tending to involve fewer participants. Larger trainings, in turn, used OpenPlato less often. These patterns suggest that the two platforms were deployed in quite different training contexts, which is relevant background for interpreting their associations with participant evaluations.

The findings also provide several insights into how training and participant characteristics relate to training assessment. Age showed very small associations with two survey items: older participants were slightly less likely to feel they had the chance to actively engage, but slightly more likely to feel the training offered sufficient flexibility for their learning needs.

Larger trainings – involving higher numbers of participants - reduced participants' sense of active engagement, pointing towards the practical constraints of facilitating participation at large scales.

Trainings with more sessions were associated with slightly higher agreement that the training taught participants many new concepts, likely because facilitators had more time to cover a greater variety of topics.

Longer sessions were associated with a greater sense that the training covered too many topics, yet also with greater perceived flexibility and slightly clearer aims and objectives, a combination that points to a trade-off between depth and focus in longer training formats.

Where OpenPlato was used, participants were less likely to feel the training covered too many topics, reinforcing the earlier finding that OpenPlato is associated with a more coherent learning experience. Where Projects was used, participants were less likely to find the materials clear or to feel the training offered sufficient flexibility, but more likely to report having had the chance to actively engage. This reflects Projects' strength in promoting interactivity during the training, while the other evaluation dimensions suggest a more mixed picture for the use of Projects.

Assessing node strength across the full network, use of the Projects platform emerged as the single most influential variable, with OpenPlato second. Overall satisfaction with the training quality came third, though with only a small gap to the variables that followed. This means that of all the training characteristics examined, whether and which digital platform, especially if it was Projects, was used appears to have the greatest relevance for how participants evaluated their experience – despite the fact that the survey item addressing evaluation of the online platforms and whether they were adequate for learning shows the lowest strength in the network.

Examining clusters within this network, three groups emerged. The first group again brought together the two negatively phrased survey items, whether the training covered too many topics and whether aims and objectives were not made clear, but this time also included active engagement during the training.

The second group contained all training and participant characteristics together: age, Projects, OpenPlato, number of sessions, number of attendees, and session length. Thus, they form a cluster of structural and training design aspects, which are more strongly related to each another than to any individual survey item.

The third group contained all remaining survey items, mirroring the largest cluster from the first network and covering individual evaluations of the training experience.

- 1: The training materials were clear.
- 2: The training materials were relevant and up to date.
- 3: It seemed to me that the training tried to cover too many topics.
- 4: The training taught me a lot of new concepts.
- 5: I managed to complete the requirements of the training without feeling unduly stressed.
- 6: The training provided sufficient flexibility for my personal learning needs.
- 7: The training was well structured.
- 8: I was given the chance to actively engage during the training.
- 9: The aims and objectives of this training were NOT made very clear.
- 10: The online platforms used in the training were adequate tools for learning.
- 11: During the training, my interest in the topic was increased.
- 12: Overall, the training experience was worthwhile.
- 13: Overall, I'm satisfied with the quality of this training.
- 14: age
- 15: Nr of participants who attended
- 16: Nr of training sessions
- 17: length per session in hours
- 18: Used OpenPlato
- 19: Used Projects

Figure 21: Network of training evaluation and training/participant characteristics.

5.3 Evaluation activity and extension of participant questionnaire

5.3.1 Question 1: Which aspects of the training did you enjoy?

Responses to this question were highly varied in length and specificity, ranging from single-word answers to detailed evaluative statements. Across the full set of coded segments, several recurring themes emerged: the interactive format of the trainings, opportunities for discussion and peer exchange, practical exercises and real-life examples, the quality of the trainers, the acquisition of new and relevant knowledge, and the overall atmosphere and structure of the sessions. These themes were observed across thematic areas, training formats, and career stages, though with some variation in emphasis. Isolated negative assessments were also recorded and are reported separately below.

5.3.1.1 Interactivity

The most widely appreciated aspect of the trainings was their interactive format. Participants across virtually all thematic areas and career stages highlighted interactivity as a key source of enjoyment, frequently referencing specific interactive elements such as group activities, quizzes, polls, and Q&A sessions. This pattern can be considered the dominant finding for this question, with no obvious differences by gender or career stage – early career researchers, senior scientists, and librarians cited interactivity as a highlight.

Representative responses illustrate the broadness of this appreciation. One participant noted that „it was interactive and we could get answers to the questions” (D 55), while another described the training as „an interactive journey for me learning a topic that I’m slightly new [to]” (D 93). A participant from a FAIR data management training stated that „being conducted interactively made it easier for me to concentrate” (D 121), and another described „our interactive participation in the training and experiencing the information explained through examples firsthand” as what they most enjoyed (D 122). A participant in an online training noted that „the structure of the training was interactive and the environment was friendly allowing us to have wonderful discussions” (D 45).

The use of specific interactive tools was also explicitly appreciated. In one instance, a participant described how the trainer „captured our attention from the start with the Menti he used” (D 81), while others mentioned web surveys (D 79), instant quizzes (D 93), and self-testing modules (D 160; D 168) as highlights. One participant valued the „gradual testing of understanding of all concepts” and „the variety of tools and types of questionnaires” (D 160). A doctoral student in a FAIR data management training valued „the breakout rooms, and the daily assignments,” noting that „these made me feel involved in the training and not only a receiver” (D 88).

5.3.1.2 Discussion and peer exchange

Closely related to interactivity but distinct in character was the appreciation for structured and open discussions among participants. This theme was particularly pronounced in Management and Leadership trainings and Citizen Science trainings, where group discussion was often the primary pedagogical method. It was notably

consistent among doctoral students and postdoctoral researchers, who frequently emphasised the value of exchanging experiences with peers at similar career stages, though it appeared across all career stages represented in the data.

Multiple participants from Management and Leadership sessions explicitly named discussions as the highlight of the training. One stated that „the best aspects were discussions where we found tips and tricks. I felt confident to exchange opinions and experiences” (D 127). Another appreciated „the dialogue style of the presenters, instead of a presenting style. Interactive with participants, and giving feedback to participants’ comments” (D 135). A postdoctoral researcher noted what they enjoyed most was „to know that I am not alone with my experiences and other need coping strategies too” (D 135), reflecting a social-emotional dimension of peer exchange. Similarly, one participant valued „hearing other people’s experience” (D 156), and another described „brainstorming with so many different perspectives and being able to walk away with tools for the workplace” (D 159).

In Citizen Science trainings with a predominantly bachelor’s-level participant group, discussion was almost universally cited and showed the strongest concentration of this theme across any subgroup in the dataset. This pattern was most pronounced in a single in-person training session (D 150), from which the majority of responses in this subgroup originate, and should be interpreted accordingly. Participants from that session described appreciating both the format’s balance between group work and plenary discussion – „it was nice that it switched between class discussion and group work so that the individual parts weren’t too long” (D 150) – and the low-pressure environment it created: „being out in groups and not having to present, but that there was a joint discussion at the end removes the pressure to finish a product and instead promotes having thought good thoughts” (D 150). Corroborating evidence from other Citizen Science trainings, though less detailed, points in the same direction: participants valued the exchange with peers and described taking discussions back to their research groups as a key outcome (D 106), while others highlighted networking and practice exchange as among the most applicable aspects of the training (D 104).

In a Science Communication training, a participant observed that „conversations in class were very rewarding. Many things were clarified by hearing others’ arguments and viewpoints” (D 180).

5.3.1.3 Practical exercises, real-life examples, and case studies

Practical application of content was widely appreciated across thematic areas, career stages, and training formats. Participants valued exercises, case studies, hands-on tasks, and real-world examples, frequently contrasting these positively with more theoretical instruction. One participant in a FAIR data management training gave a detailed account: „I particularly enjoyed the practical aspects of the training, especially the sections explaining how to organize, store and document research data effectively. The examples and tools presented helped me understand how to apply good data management practices in my own research. I also appreciated the clear structure of the seminar and the opportunity to discuss real challenges related to data handling in academic projects” (D 120). Another in the same training noted that „the

training being hands-on and sufficiently emphasizing the resources needed to adapt the given information to our daily lives are the points I liked most" (D 120).

In Open Access trainings, practical exercises around journal evaluation were specifically appreciated. One senior scientist remarked: „I really liked critically examining articles to decide if they are appropriate journals to publish in. I think this practice was great and I will pay more attention to critically examining journals and conferences in the future" (D 121). A participant in another Open Access training noted that „the practical exercise of creating a publication plan based on the project and funding requirements was very useful to apply the concepts of open access, rights retention, and funder mandates in a concrete scenario" (D 127).

Real-life examples and case studies were frequently cited across thematic areas (D 123; D 135; D 55; D 137). From a Gender, Non-Discrimination and Inclusion training, one postdoctoral researcher appreciated „very useful tips on how to best implement a gender perspective in a proposal for Horizon Europe" and added: „I really appreciated the case studies that were presented as they were simplified versions of research projects that allow me to understand even though Life Sciences is not my field of experience" (D 123). In Management and Leadership trainings, the use of fictional scenarios was particularly appreciated as a safe entry point for personal reflection: „It was nice to first talk about a fictional scenario and not directly about your own experiences. You can learn from that without the need to directly be really open about your own experiences with people you do not know" (D 157). No systematic differences by career stage or gender were observed regarding the appreciation of practical elements.

5.3.1.4 *Trainer and presenter quality*

Numerous participants explicitly attributed their positive experience to the quality, approachability, and expertise of the trainers. Appreciation ranged from brief acknowledgements to detailed characterisations. One participant from a FAIR data management training wrote: „I really liked the presenter, she was clear, engaging, and approachable. I also appreciated that there were many real-life examples, which made the content easier to understand and apply in practice" (D 137). From an Open Access training, one participant observed: „the speaker was so well prepared, showed the structure of the presentation and made the goals of the lecture very clear. He spoke very well, and even increased my interest in the topic" (D 102). A senior scientist praised a trainer for making „complex topics easy to understand and kept the sessions interesting" (D 50). In one Management and Leadership session, trainers were specifically praised for adopting an open, participatory style, with one participant noting they „were really open-minded, asking us our opinions as well, it was pleasant and they made me feel seen" (D 135).

Trainer approachability and openness to questions were cited positively across career stages. „The instructors were very open to communication and our curiosities were satisfied" (D 81) and „the trainers were very good. They made an otherwise boring subject interesting" (D 31) are representative. Notably, early career researchers – particularly master's students and doctoral students – appeared somewhat more likely to explicitly mention trainer personality and communication style as a source of enjoyment, while senior participants more often referenced trainer expertise and

depth of knowledge. This distinction is observable in the data but should be interpreted with caution given the uneven distribution of career stages across the responses.

5.3.1.5 Acquisition of new and relevant knowledge

A recurring theme – particularly among participants newer to the training topics – was the appreciation for gaining knowledge previously unknown to them. This was especially prominent in Open Access and FAIR data management trainings. Typical responses included: „I have learned what citizen science is” (D 104), „I learned FAIR term and apply to my future research” (D 31), and „as someone who is at the beginning of my academic studies, I have gained a lot of knowledge on a subject I have no knowledge about” (D 55). One participant from a Citizen Science training reflected: „it was generally just exciting to have my eyes opened to a new concept that I didn’t know much about beforehand” (D 150).

The relevance of the knowledge to participants’ immediate research context was also noted: „I learned a lot of things I had never heard about before, and they are very important for my research” (D 66). This theme was most pronounced among doctoral students and early career researchers, who more frequently described the training content as entirely new to them. Senior scientists tended to appreciate the updating of existing knowledge rather than acquiring it from scratch – for instance, noting that new trends or policy developments were highlighted – though this distinction was not universal. A librarian and administrative staff member highlighted a distinctive benefit: „As a librarian it is very useful for me to learn more about the financial part of the research process which I usually don’t have the opportunity to hear much about” (D 101), indicating that the same training could serve different professional needs for different participant profiles.

5.3.1.6 Structure, clarity, and atmosphere

Clarity of presentation and a well-organised training structure were appreciated by a considerable number of participants, often in the context of an otherwise complex or unfamiliar subject matter. Responses such as „light and well-prepared structure and content” (D 31), „it was well structured and easy to understand” (D 32), and „the simplicity and immediacy of the presentation of the concepts so that they can be understood even by people who come into contact with data management for the first time” (D 163) suggest that clarity and accessibility were important quality markers. No clear differences by gender or career stage were observable for this theme.

The atmosphere of the trainings was also positively noted, particularly in in-person sessions. Participants described the environment as „friendly” (D 45), „relaxed” (D 86), and characterised by a „nice and safe atmosphere” (D 154). In several Citizen Science trainings, a „friendly environment” was mentioned explicitly (D 76), and group activities were described as facilitating socialisation beyond the learning content itself (D 93).

5.3.1.7 *Negative responses and outliers*

A small number of participants provided explicitly negative or disappointed responses. One participant from a Science Communication training stated simply „I did not learn much” (D 61), while a peer from the same training noted that „the speaker was a good entertainer but a lot of things he said were well-known” (D 61), suggesting that content level was insufficient for participants with prior familiarity with the subject. From a Citizen Science training, one participant responded „Nothing” (D 146), and the same response appeared in two further documents (D 91; D 178). One participant expressed dissatisfaction with a mismatch between the advertised scope of a Management and Leadership webinar and its actual content focus, noting that the training „didn’t meet my expectations” due to this discrepancy (D 148). A participant in a FAIR data management training noted that „it was not an interactive training involving teamwork and interaction” (D 172), directly contrasting with the majority of responses and suggesting a format difference in that particular session. Technical difficulties in online formats were noted by isolated participants, affecting their overall experience independently of content quality (D 101; D 178).

5.3.2 *Question 2: In what ways was the training useful to you?*

Responses to this question were among the most substantive and reflective in the dataset, with many participants articulating specific ways in which the training content connected to their professional or personal circumstances. Several distinct themes emerged: the acquisition of new knowledge and conceptual understanding, direct professional and research applicability, awareness raising – particularly around rights, policies, and biases – the utility of practical tools and resources, and, in the domain of Management and Leadership, a pronounced psychological and social dimension centred on solidarity and self-reflection. Where document variables were available, career stage emerged as the most consequential differentiating factor, with notably distinct patterns of perceived usefulness between early career researchers, senior academics, and librarians or administrative staff.

5.3.2.1 *Knowledge acquisition and conceptual understanding*

The most broadly cited form of usefulness was the acquisition of new or clarified knowledge. This pattern was consistent across thematic areas and career stages, though its character varied. For many participants – particularly those at earlier career stages encountering topics such as Open Access, FAIR data management, or research integrity for the first time – the training represented a decisive introduction to previously unknown concepts. One doctoral student described the usefulness of an Open Access training with particular directness: „As a prospective academic, I had never encountered such comprehensive and detailed content before. This kind of know-how is usually learned by trial and error along the way. With this training, I actually prevented many falls” (D 121). Another early career participant noted: „issues that I wasn’t aware of came to my attention and now I have a much clearer understanding of the subject” (D 176).

For participants with some prior exposure to the topics, the training served a consolidating or updating function. A senior scientist noted plainly: „I realised my knowledge is outdated” (D 127), while another described the training as useful for

„refreshing the knowledge” and gaining information on EU-related aspects (D 32). A postdoctoral researcher stated that „it helped me reorganize and consolidate some concepts” (D 82), and a librarian reported having „updated my knowledge” (D 119). This distinction between first-time acquisition and knowledge updating was observable across career stages: early career researchers and master’s students more frequently described the training as entirely new to them, while senior scientists and postdoctoral researchers more often framed it as extending or correcting existing understanding. No systematic differences by gender were observable for this theme.

5.3.2.2 Direct applicability to research practice and professional tasks

A second major theme was the concrete applicability of training content to participants’ ongoing or planned research activities. This was particularly pronounced in FAIR data management and Open Access trainings, where participants frequently connected the content directly to their theses, upcoming publications, funding obligations, or data management plans. One doctoral student in a FAIR data management training gave a detailed account: „The training was very useful because it clarified how to plan and manage research data throughout an entire project. I gained a better understanding of data organization, storage, and documentation, as well as important issues such as confidentiality and ethical handling of sensitive information” (D 120). A master’s student was more concise but equally concrete: „I have learned useful information that I will use while writing my thesis” (D 93). Another participant connected the training directly to an impending publication milestone: „I will be publishing articles in the near future” (D 107), while a doctoral student with external funding noted: „I am a PhD student with a [national funding body] funding and I have to be aware of the conditions of publication” (D 103).

Applicability to journal selection was cited frequently in Open Access trainings. „I learned new and extremely useful tricks needed for finding the best journal option” (D 127) and „The training will enable me to choose journals to submit my manuscripts to with greater ease and quality” (D 100) are representative. The training also prompted some participants to reformulate existing practices: one master’s student described how the training „enabled me questioning the data collection and management in my current projects. After the seminar, I decided to back-up my data in different cloud services” (D 93).

Early career researchers were most likely to describe applicability in concrete, near-future terms (thesis, first publication, upcoming project). Senior scientists tended to describe applicability in terms of publication planning, funder compliance, or broader research strategy.

5.3.2.3 Professional role enhancement for support staff

A particularly distinct pattern emerged among participants identifying as librarians, administrative staff, research managers, or similar support roles. For this group, perceived usefulness was systematically framed not in terms of personal research benefit but in terms of improved capacity to serve and advise researchers. Representative responses include: „I work in faculty library and professors often need help with publishing articles and publishers” (D 100), „I will especially benefit from it in reference librarianship” (D 90), „I can answer the questions of academics and students

in my institution more clearly" (D 121), and „as a librarian, I can support academics in a more equipped manner on these issues" (D 55). A research policy officer described the usefulness in institutional terms: „I gained practical tools and materials that we can seamlessly integrate into our existing programs tailored for researchers" (D 148). A science manager noted: „I work as a science manager at this university, so this way I can be more useful to my researchers" (D 178). This pattern of other-directed usefulness was unique to this career group and did not appear among researchers describing personal use.

5.3.2.4 Awareness raising: rights, policies, and biases

A thematically significant form of usefulness was the raising of awareness, which is distinct from knowledge acquisition in that participants emphasised a shift in perspective or consciousness rather than the learning of specific facts. This was particularly prominent in Open Access and Gender, Non-Discrimination and Inclusion trainings.

In Open Access contexts, awareness of author rights was a recurring focal point. „I haven't considered my author rights when signing contracts in the past. I will definitely be much more careful in the future" (D 101) and „I learned about my rights. I learned that I need to protect these rights and how I can do so" (D 55) reflect a pattern of participants becoming conscious of rights and risks they had previously overlooked. One doctoral student expressed this shift in notable terms: „I had a better understanding of intellectual property rights. But more importantly I realised that, I, a potential future scientist, am not a mule that is disconnected with its product, but I am a human and I have rights" (D 121). Awareness of predatory journals and fake conferences was similarly cited as a key form of usefulness, particularly by participants at mid- and senior career levels: „Warnings about predatory journals and fake publishing were crucial" (D 90).

In Gender, Non-Discrimination and Inclusion trainings, awareness of unconscious bias was cited as the primary form of usefulness. „This training has been valuable to me, as it has made me more aware of how prevalent certain biases are and how they can be unintentionally reinforced. Identifying them in a structured way has been especially helpful" (D 34). A postdoctoral researcher working in a research management capacity noted the usefulness of being able to „transfer the knowledge to the researchers I assist" (D 123), while a senior scientist described the training as useful „for thinking and structuring new projects" in light of the gender dimension (D 123). Research managers and administrators in this thematic area consistently described a dual usefulness: personal awareness on the one hand, and improved capacity to integrate gender considerations into project proposals and institutional programmes on the other.

5.3.2.5 Practical tools and resources

Across Open Access, FAIR data management, and Citizen Science trainings, many participants cited access to specific tools, platforms, databases, and links as a key form of usefulness. This was a distinct sub-theme, particularly prominent among participants who appreciated concrete takeaways they could apply immediately. Representative responses include references to the Journal Checker Tool, Creative

Commons licences and the CC Chooser tool, data repositories such as Zenodo and Aperta, and funder-specific platforms. One doctoral student articulated the value of this systematically: the training covered „protecting our rights over the work as the copyright holder and licensing options (especially via Creative Commons licenses). Methods of sharing while ‘protecting author rights’ in open access publishing. Compliance with funder policies through Plan S principles and the ‘Rights Retention Strategy’ practice” (D 92). Access to curated, reliable resources was especially appreciated by participants who described the training as a shortcut to information they would otherwise have had to locate themselves.

5.3.2.6 *Psychological and social utility in Management and Leadership trainings*

The Management and Leadership trainings – particularly those centred on doctoral wellbeing, imposter syndrome, work-life balance, boundary-setting, and professional identity – resulted in a specific pattern of perceived usefulness centred on psychological and social dimensions. The most frequently recurring theme was a sense of solidarity: the recognition that one’s struggles are shared by others. Participants described this across multiple documents with notable consistency: „I realised I am not alone, for instance now I know I am not the only person to feel frustrated. I think it was useful also to learn new strategies to face difficult situations” (D 135), „it gave me a sense of togetherness in an otherwise often competitive and dividing research landscape. It helps lower the stigma associated with mental health topics” (D 135), „I came to understand that this feeling of not doing or being enough is not something I am feeling because I am doing anything wrong but something a lot of people feel” (D 71), and „it did contribute to my sense of belonging in academia and recognize that we are all experiencing similar struggles in different ways” (D 159). This theme was so consistent across Management and Leadership documents that it can be considered a defining characteristic of this thematic area’s perceived usefulness.

Alongside solidarity, participants described usefulness in terms of self-reflection, the acquisition of coping strategies, and the development of vocabulary for articulating challenges: „It gave me the perspective that when I pause and reflect, and write down my problems and strengths, I can truly find a solution to the situation that I can move towards” (D 86), „to put words on some problematics I have as a post-doc” (D 135), and „to learn new words and terms to communicate particular dilemmas” (D 157). Participants also cited concrete tools for improving professional life: „it helped me gain more awareness of the topic and in strategies that I can implement to address imposter feelings” (D 157), and „I am the chair of the PhD council at my institution and have been working on ways to boost the feeling of community among ECRs. This gives me concrete tools to better manage my cohort and help them through their studies” (D 159).

This psychological and social dimension was predominantly expressed by doctoral students and postdoctoral researchers, for whom the topics addressed appeared to resonate with immediate lived experience. Where participants with other roles commented on usefulness in this domain, they tended to do so in terms of institutional relevance or perspective-broadening rather than personal identification with the content.

5.3.2.7 *Negative responses and outliers*

A small number of participants indicated limited or no personal usefulness. In one Science Communication training, a subset of bachelor's-level participants described the content as not reaching beyond their prior knowledge, pointing to a perceived mismatch between content level and existing familiarity (D 180). A more nuanced variant of this pattern appeared in a Management and Leadership training, where one participant noted that whilst the informational content was not new to them, the relational dimension – knowing that others share the same experiences – remained valuable (D 157). Similarly, a participant with prior experience in Citizen Science found the content more limited in terms of new information, whilst still valuing the opportunity for networking and exchange (D 104). Taken together, these responses suggest a ceiling effect for participants who arrive with substantial prior knowledge or experience, rather than a fundamental criticism of the training content itself.

5.3.3 *Question 3: Which skills did you gain?*

Responses to this question were more heterogeneous and, in some cases, more tentative than those for the preceding questions. A recurring pattern across thematic areas and career stages was participants' explicit hesitation to characterise what they had gained as „skills“ in the strict sense, frequently framing their gains as knowledge, awareness, or inspiration that might in time develop into operational skills. This distinction, raised by several participants, is itself a finding worth highlighting. Where concrete skills were reported, they clustered into several distinct categories: research data management and documentation, journal selection and publication navigation, copyright and author rights management, critical thinking and evaluation, interpersonal and self-management competencies in the Management and Leadership domain, and science communication competencies.

5.3.3.1 *The knowledge–skills distinction: a recurring qualification*

Across several thematic areas, participants explicitly distinguished between gaining knowledge and gaining skills, often expressing uncertainty about whether the training had produced transferable, actionable competencies. This distinction suggests that single-session trainings may be well positioned to generate awareness and conceptual understanding, whilst the consolidation of knowledge into operational skills requires further practice and application over time. This was articulated directly by one participant: „Skills are developed through practice. This was too short a time to develop new skills, but it was useful for raising awareness about developing the skill“ (D 136). The pattern was visible across thematic areas – in Citizen Science trainings (D 104; D 105; D 106), Research Integrity (D 41), Management and Leadership (D 135; D 157), and Science Communication (D 58) – and was particularly pronounced among participants with prior exposure to the topic, for whom the training served a consolidating rather than skill-building function. As one postdoctoral researcher noted: „Personally, I don't think I have learned new skills [...] However, I feel it is enormously important that more people get to know about it and the conversation keeps going!“ (D 135).

5.3.3.2 *Research data management and documentation*

In FAIR data management trainings, participants reported the most clearly delineated technical skill gains of any thematic area. Skills around organising, storing, documenting, and sharing research data were consistently cited, often with reference to specific competencies. A doctoral student reported: „Through the training, I gained practical skills in organising and structuring research data, selecting appropriate storage solutions, and creating clear documentation and metadata” (D 120). Another summarised a broad set of competencies: „I learned the meaning of open science, how to store data in repositories, how to create a Data Management Plan (DMP), how to raise the profile of my work, and how to adhere to the FAIR principles” (D 161). Multiple participants cited DMP writing specifically as a skill gained (D 93; D 96; D 137; D 163), and one senior scientist specified: „I have learned how to create a good readme file, how to write a better DMP, how to critically read DMPs” (D 137). The practical skill of depositing data in repositories was also noted (D 66; D 137; D 93), alongside knowledge of metadata structures and formats (D 94; D 172).

These skills were reported across career stages, though the framing differed: master’s students tended to describe understanding of FAIR concepts and DMP planning in general terms, while doctoral students and postdoctoral researchers more often articulated specific procedural competencies tied to active projects. Senior scientists and librarians in this domain more frequently described skill gains in terms of understanding systems and tools rather than personal data handling.

5.3.3.3 *Journal selection, publication navigation, and predatory journal detection*

In Open Access trainings, a clearly defined cluster of skills emerged around evaluating journals and navigating the publication process. Participants described gaining skills in identifying suitable journals, assessing journal quality and policies, recognising predatory journals, and using verification platforms. One participant described this range: „I gained skills in planning research publications according to funder requirements, navigating open access models, assessing journal policies and APC costs, and retaining author rights. The training also improved my ability to apply these concepts in practice and make informed decisions about where and how to publish research outputs” (D 127). Another reported gaining „the ability to analyse good journals and to be alert to publication policies” (D 103). The skill of detecting predatory journals was explicitly named by several participants (D 118; D 90; D 96; D 82), and one postdoctoral researcher stated concisely: „I can say that it is my ability to distinguish between predatory journals and real scientific journals” (D 90).

Specific tools and platforms were cited as newly acquired competencies, including the Journal Checker Tool, DOAJ, and Open Policy Finder (D 50; D 90; D 101). One librarian provided a particularly detailed account of a multi-layered skill set gained, encompassing copyright management, open access dissemination strategies, funder requirements, and academic profiling platforms (D 50). This career group – librarians and support staff – again showed a distinct orientation, describing skills in terms of advising others and supporting researchers rather than personal publishing practice.

Doctoral students and master’s students most frequently described journal selection and predatory journal awareness as newly acquired competencies, reflecting the

practical immediacy of these skills for researchers approaching their first publications. A bachelor's-level participant noted that following the training „I will no longer make potentially dangerous mistakes when publishing articles” (D 50), a statement reflecting the protective function of this skill set for early career researchers.

5.3.3.4 Copyright and author rights management

Closely related but distinct was a cluster of skills around copyright management and author rights, particularly prominent in Open Access trainings. Participants described gaining skills in applying Creative Commons licences, understanding rights transfer agreements, and navigating rights retention strategies. One doctoral student gave a systematic account: „I gained skills in understanding and managing copyright, open access publishing processes, and the use of Creative Commons licenses. I also learned the importance of proper archiving for accessibility and long-term preservation” (D 91). Another described gains specifically in „selecting appropriate Creative Commons licenses and managing copyright in academic publishing” (D 92). The Rights Retention Strategy was cited as a practical competency by several participants (D 92; D 50). Skills around knowing when and how to retain copyright before signing a publisher agreement were noted across career stages, with both junior and senior researchers describing a shift in their awareness of what they could legally claim and how to do so.

5.3.3.5 Critical thinking and evaluation skills

A transversal skill that appeared across multiple thematic areas was critical thinking or evaluative capacity. In Open Access trainings, this manifested as the ability to critically examine journals and publishing practices (D 100; D 102; D 121; D 166; D 179). In Science Communication trainings, critical reading of media, language use, and metaphor was the primary skill cited. Participants described gaining „the ability to notice and critically engage with metaphors” (D 180) and becoming „more critical of articles and their use of metaphors” (D 180), alongside broader gains in source-critical thinking (D 180). In the Management and Leadership domain, one participant cited „to question existing structures in academia and take even more agency” (D 158) as a skill gain. These formulations suggest that critical thinking competencies, while described in diverse terms, constituted a cross-cutting skill outcome across thematic areas.

5.3.3.6 Interpersonal and self-management competencies

In Management and Leadership trainings, the skills reported were qualitatively different from those in the other thematic areas, centring on interpersonal communication, boundary-setting, self-reflection, and psychological coping. The boundary-setting training generated the most concrete self-reported skill gains in this domain: participants described skills such as „using assertive statements that help me set boundaries clearly and politely” (D 136) and – formulated very concretely – „Say NO!” (D 136), alongside broader confidence gains and increased clarity about their own rights. Communication skills more broadly were also cited, including „skills to talk about the topic of social safety” (D 158) and „a vocabulary around social safety

and wellness” (D 158), as well as „a vocabulary around identity and how to lead useful productive conversations about it” (D 159).

Self-reflection and self-awareness were frequently named as skills in this domain. Participants described gains in „reflection and identity mapping” (D 159), „more self-reflection, identifying my needs and standing up for them” (D 71), and related introspective capacities (D 70). Coping and stress-management strategies were also reported, including „solutions for short term stress reduction” (D 135), „new strategies to organise my work better” (D 135), „strategies to handle work-life balance” (D 155), and „facing stressful situations better” (D 70).

One particularly detailed response from a research manager and support professional described a comprehensive set of institutional competencies gained, including „resource curation and implementation,” „strategic support mapping,” „program development,” and „needs assessment” for researcher wellbeing (D 148), illustrating how participants in non-researcher roles translated the same training content into a specific skill profile.

These interpersonal and self-management skill gains were almost exclusively reported by doctoral students and postdoctoral researchers in Management and Leadership trainings. No clear gender-based differences were observed for this category.

5.3.3.7 *Networking*

In Citizen Science trainings particularly, networking was described as a skill or outcome, though most participants who named it framed it as a by-product rather than a core competency. Phrases such as „tools for my own projects but more important: networking” (D 76), „I got new contacts and know-how” (D 104), and „networking, practice exchange” (D 145) appeared several times. In the broader dataset, networking as a discrete skill outcome appeared only in contexts where the training format explicitly included structured peer exchange.

5.3.3.8 *Outliers and negative responses*

A notable minority of participants stated explicitly that they had not gained skills, mostly among those with prior familiarity with the subject matter or those attending shorter, introductory sessions. In one Science Communication training, responses such as „I did not gain any skills” and „more so a reminder of the topic than new skills” (D 180) were representative of this subgroup. In Management and Leadership trainings, some participants responded with „None” or „Not applicable” (D 71), while another noted that the training did not meet their expectation for skill-building (D 157). One senior scientist noted a limitation in skill consolidation that may apply more broadly: that completing the training in full would have been necessary to properly transform knowledge into skills (D 33), suggesting that format constraints may have limited skill development for some participants.

5.3.4 *Question 4: What specifically can you apply in practice?*

Responses to this question were among the most concrete and action-oriented across the entire evaluation, with many participants articulating specific behavioural

changes, procedural steps, or institutional actions they intended to undertake as a result of the training. The themes align closely with those identified in Questions 2 and 3, but with stronger emphasis on prospective application rather than retrospective description of learnings. Key areas of practical application include: research data management and documentation practices, informed journal selection and publication decision-making, copyright management and rights retention, personal wellbeing and self-management strategies, and the use of training content to support colleagues, students, or library users. Differences by career stage and professional role are again visible, with librarians and support staff consistently framing application in terms of advising and training others, while researchers describe personal research practice.

5.3.4.1 Research data management: immediate application at project level

In FAIR data management trainings, practical application was articulated with notable specificity, and many participants described actions they intended to begin immediately or at the outset of their next project. The Data Management Plan (DMP) was the most consistently cited practical output: participants across career stages described plans to write or improve a DMP, with doctoral and master's students frequently connecting this to their ongoing thesis work. One doctoral student gave a detailed account of their intended practice: „In practice, I can now apply structured methods for organising and storing my research data, ensuring that files are consistently named and safely backed up. I can also create clearer documentation and metadata so that my datasets remain understandable and reusable over time. Additionally, I can apply the principles of ethical data handling – especially when dealing with sensitive information – and develop a complete data management plan for my research projects” (D 120). Another described concrete next steps: „Preparing a plan for data management before the start of my projects, using CC licensing, using platforms to store my data” (D 93). A master's student noted: „The plan of data management will be useful as I am just starting my thesis” (D 93), reflecting the practical immediacy of the content for those at the beginning of research careers.

README file creation was specifically cited as an immediately applicable technique by multiple participants (D 31; D 32; D 33; D 137), as was the use of open file formats, cloud-based backup services, and data repositories. One participant described a clear and actionable intent: „Structuring my data better, focus on open file formats” (D 137), while another planned to „use tools for creating DMP and tool for testing fairness of data” (D 128). Senior scientists in this domain were more likely to describe application in terms of project setup and institutional dissemination: one stated she intended „data management planning before project setup” (D 128), and another planned to integrate FAIR principles into an ongoing EU project (D 33).

Librarians and support staff consistently described the content as applicable to their advisory and training functions. One librarian planned to „use published templates for data management and share it with my grad students” (D 119), and another described plans to „help researchers with questions pertaining to FAIR principles and filling out their DMPs” (D 135). This pattern of other-directed application was consistently pronounced in this group across all thematic areas.

5.3.4.2 *Informed journal selection and publication decision-making*

In Open Access trainings, the most consistently cited practical application was the ability to select journals more critically and navigate the publication process more effectively. Participants described plans to verify journal quality before submission, check publisher policies, avoid predatory journals, and apply their knowledge of open access models to ongoing and future publications. One participant expressed this simply: „Looking at journals closely before submitting articles, understanding what publishers are asking me to consent to after acceptance” (D 121). Another planned to „take good care of which journal I choose for publishing and what I sign” (D 101), and a postdoctoral researcher described acquiring a practical tool for this process: „I now have a checklist to check when uploading my papers” (D 90).

Alignment with funder requirements was an application particularly often reported by participants working on or anticipating EU-funded projects. Participants described intended applications such as planning „publication costs in advance and consider free publishing options” (D 127), using the Journal Checker Tool to verify compliance (D 101; D 50), and adjusting their publishing preferences to meet funder mandates. A doctoral student with external funding described the training as directly relevant: „I am a PhD student with a [national funding body] funding and I have to be aware of the conditions of publication” (D 103), while a senior scientist noted the importance of knowing the rules in the context of funded research (D 178).

This application domain was broadly consistent across career stages. Doctoral students and master’s students oriented the application towards their first publications; postdoctoral researchers framed it in terms of ongoing publication strategies; senior scientists described it in the context of broader publication planning for research groups, including supporting students and co-authors.

5.3.4.3 *Copyright management and rights retention in practice*

A specific cluster of practical applications concerned the active management of copyright and author rights. Participants described plans to apply Creative Commons licences to their own work, use rights retention strategies, submit author addendum letters alongside manuscripts, and avoid signing away rights inadvertently. One doctoral student described this set of planned actions: „Writing cover letter for Author Accepted Manuscripts (AAM) (preprint copy), using Creative Commons licenses, Diamond Open Access” (D 50). Another planned to use the SPARC Author Addendum to retain key rights at the point of submission (D 92). A postdoctoral researcher articulated a behavioural change: „I will pay attention when uploading articles to journals in the choice of my copyrights” (D 50), and a librarian described a planned precaution: „Read the contracts very carefully before signing. Looking for Open Access Journals that charge subscription fees and guaranteeing my copyright” (D 179).

Librarians and support staff again described this content in terms of advising others: one planned to „suggest to scientists the use of various tools: Coalition S templates, SPARC author addendum, explanation of CC licenses, Journal Checker Tool, DOAJ search” (D 101), and another described plans to organise training sessions and advocacy work in academic circles (D 50). This group demonstrated the clearest

alignment between training content and professional function across all thematic areas.

5.3.4.4 Wellbeing and self-management: behavioural and relational applications

In Management and Leadership trainings, practical applications were predominantly personal and behavioural, centring on changes to how participants planned to manage their working lives, relationships, and emotional responses. Boundary-setting in professional relationships was the most concrete application in the boundary-related training session: participants described plans to use assertive communication techniques in setting limits (D 136), to „set boundaries more often in the future” (D 136), and to „say clearly and out loud what I think” (D 136).

In the Management and Leadership trainings, participants described a range of specific behavioural changes: „organising my work day and cutting down on unnecessary multitasking” (D 86), „cognitive crafting to get a different perspective when perfectionism or procrastination takes over” (D 86), „starting to say ‘no’, taking my time to reflect more on proposals; starting to do realistic and less stressing to-do lists” (D 135), and „I will decrease perfectionism” (D 70). Seeking help proactively was also cited: „Seek help when feeling overwhelmed” (D 70), and „take care of myself before I reach stressful situations and build a support system” (D 71). Self-reflection tools, such as identity mapping exercises (D 159) and monthly reflection practices (D 72), were mentioned as planned ongoing practices.

These applications were almost entirely personal in character among doctoral and postdoctoral researchers. Where participants in support, management, or senior roles described application, the orientation shifted towards institutional action: one senior research manager planned to provide coordinators with „a curated toolkit of the resources identified in the training, enabling them to embed mental health modules directly into their existing PhD and researcher development curriculums” (D 148), and another described exploring „protocols and guides for PhD supervisors” (D 148). A doctoral student who chaired their institution’s PhD council described a directly applied institutional purpose: „This gives me concrete tools to better manage my cohort and help them through their studies” (D 159).

5.3.4.5 Gender integration in research design and proposal writing

In Gender, Non-Discrimination and Inclusion trainings, practical applications were oriented towards integrating a gender perspective into research design, proposals, and science communication. Multiple participants described plans to apply the SAGER guidelines, address the gender dimension in Horizon Europe proposals, avoid superficial gender inclusion, and consider gender differences throughout the research design rather than only at the reporting stage. One senior scientist stated: „I will avoid removing gender dimension in clinical studies when results are neutral” (D 123), and another planned to „put attention to gender in writing papers, applications, presenting data” (D 123). A research management professional described a direct and transferable application: „Use the examples in supporting researchers and disseminate SAGER guidelines” (D 123). One participant gave particular detail: „Not pinkwashing, but thoroughly integrating sex, gender, and intersectionality into every step of the project” (D 123), while a doctoral student described a design-level

application: „Designing a study with sex differences from the very first step and including neutral findings, such as no sex differences, in the results” (D 123).

5.3.4.6 Science communication: critical reading and writing practices

In Science Communication trainings, some participants – predominantly bachelor’s-level students – described practical applications centred on more critical engagement with scientific language, headlines, and metaphors in both their reading and their own future writing. Applications included awareness of metaphor use when reading and writing scientific articles (D 180), the ability to construct clearer, more audience-appropriate headlines (D 180), and a heightened source-critical stance when consuming media: „You can use it a lot when reading breaking headlines and fake news, that is, see through the metaphors and not be emotionally affected by them” (D 180). Several participants also described planning to apply knowledge of audience expectations in communicating their research to non-specialist audiences (D 58; D 145), and one planned to use social media more strategically for science communication (D 61).

5.3.4.7 Uncertainty and future orientation

A subset of participants expressed uncertainty or conditionality about practical application, particularly in Citizen Science trainings and some Management and Leadership sessions. Responses such as „I hope so” (D 76), „not sure about my current project” (D 104), and „I don’t know if I want to be a researcher, but I know how articles are created and how to use them. I know how to think critically” (D 150) suggest that for some participants – particularly those at the very start of their academic trajectories – the applicability of the training content was not immediately concrete. One senior scientist noted a structural mismatch between content and current professional context (D 91), and one participant expressed partial uncertainty about a specific tool: „Not much, the identity mapping is a bit nebulous and ambiguous, not sure what to use it for” (D 159). These responses are the exception rather than the rule, but they indicate that practical applicability was not uniformly experienced, and was in part dependent on the participant’s career stage, current project situation, and professional role.

5.3.4.8 Suggestions for Improvement

Some participants also noted ideas for improvement of trainings, though the number of codes for this category is comparatively small, with suggestions drawn from a limited number of documents and lacking document variable metadata, which does not allow for comparisons across thematic area or career stage. Nevertheless, the suggestions that were provided cover several recurring themes and offer useful orientation for future training design.

The most frequently recurring request was for more time – both for discussion and for practical exercises. Multiple participants noted that discussions were cut short before reaching their natural conclusion, and several explicitly wished for extended practice time. One participant noted that allowing a productive discussion to run slightly over time would be preferable to cutting it short (D 104), while another from a Science

Communication training simply stated „More time!“ (D 59). A participant in a FAIR data management training requested „further practice and appliance on DMPs and metadata creation“ (D 45), and another suggested „more opportunities for practice as there are a lot of difficult concepts for beginners“ (D 45). These responses suggest that the balance between content delivery and practice was occasionally perceived as too focused on delivery.

Closely related was a call for follow-up sessions and continuity. One participant requested „follow-up sessions with the same team and a deeper dive into the material of the original training“ (D 45), and another suggested „creating groups to continue working with afterwards“ (D 104), indicating a wish for sustained learning communities beyond single-session formats.

Several participants advocated for a stronger emphasis on real-world case studies and applied scenarios. A participant in a Research Integrity training suggested that „laying out real practical cases would be useful for understanding questionable research practices and therefore also how we as researchers partake in creating and maintaining a good research culture“ (D 41). A participant in a Citizen Science training called for „fewer presentations of projects and more knowledge on citizen science“ (D 104), and one in a Science Communication training suggested „having some examples of a good/bad science communication piece that we can analyse“ (D 58). These suggestions align with the consistent appreciation for practical elements noted across Questions 1 and 2, and reinforce the finding that participants value application over exposition.

In terms of content specificity, several Science Communication participants wished for coverage of topics not addressed in the training: how to communicate research with sceptical or resistant audiences (D 58), how to write press releases for null results (D 59), and the option to work on one’s own project material rather than a partner’s (D 59). These suggestions indicate that participants were engaged enough to have disciplinary or contextual needs that extended beyond the training’s scope – a sign of motivation rather than dissatisfaction, though worth considering in future programme design.

Regarding format and logistics, two specific requests appear: the provision of slides or preparatory reading materials in advance of the training (D 76), which would allow participants to arrive better informed and ask more targeted questions; and the inclusion of more structured breaks, noted in both FAIR data management and Citizen Science training contexts (D 45; D 104). One participant also flagged the experience of attending online as a concern following technical difficulties, noting uncertainty about how the format would function going forward (D 76).

Taken together, the suggestions point to a consistent underlying preference: participants valued the trainings positively overall, but wished for formats that allowed deeper engagement with practical application, greater continuity beyond single sessions, and more flexibility for discipline-specific needs. The relatively small volume of suggestions in this category may itself reflect general satisfaction with the training offer, but the recurrence of the themes of time, practice, and follow-up across different thematic areas makes them actionable priorities for future programme development.

5.3.5 Summary of qualitative participant evaluation

Across all four evaluation questions, the qualitative data paint a consistently positive picture of the training offer, including important nuances regarding format, depth, and participant background. The following paragraphs summarise the main findings of the qualitative participant evaluation.

Interactivity was the single most universally appreciated feature of the trainings, cited across all thematic areas, career stages, and training formats. Participants valued not only the interactive format itself but specific tools – polls, quizzes, breakout rooms, and live exercises – that made them feel active participants rather than passive recipients. Peer discussion and experience exchange emerged as a closely related and equally important theme, particularly in Management and Leadership and Citizen Science trainings, where the opportunity to hear others' experiences and recognise shared challenges was frequently described as the highlight of the session. Trainer quality was also widely acknowledged, with participants appreciating clarity, approachability, and genuine engagement with the audience.

In terms of usefulness, the acquisition of new knowledge was the most broadly cited benefit, with some differences emerging based on career stage: early career researchers most frequently described the training content as entirely new to them, while senior researchers framed it as updating or consolidating existing knowledge. A structurally distinct pattern emerged for librarians and support staff, who consistently described usefulness in terms of enhanced capacity to advise and support researchers – a finding that is to be expected given these roles but nonetheless important to document as outcome. In Management and Leadership trainings, the dominant form of usefulness was psychological and social: participants valued the sense of solidarity, the normalisation of shared struggles, and the development of coping vocabulary, more than any specific informational content.

The question of skills gained revealed an important structural finding: many participants explicitly distinguished between gaining knowledge and gaining skills, noting that single-session formats are well suited to generating awareness and orientation but less well positioned to produce fully consolidated, transferable competencies. This observation was made by participants across multiple thematic areas and career stages. Where concrete skills were reported, they were mostly articulated in FAIR data management trainings (DMP writing, README files, data organisation), Open Access trainings (journal selection, predatory journal detection, copyright management), and boundary-setting sessions within the Management and Leadership strand.

Responses regarding practical application confirmed and extended these patterns, with participants describing specific, imminent actions they intended to undertake – from writing their first DMP to retaining author rights in an upcoming submission, adjusting their approach to work-life balance, or integrating a gender dimension into an ongoing project. Research support staff again described application in terms of advising and training others rather than personal research practice.

Suggestions for improvement were relatively few: more time, more practice opportunities, follow-up sessions, and, where possible, pre-reading materials to enable deeper engagement during the session itself.

5.4 Facilitators' reflection

5.4.1 Accessibility of the topic

Overall, the accessibility of the topic for participants varied depending on their prior knowledge, the structure of the course, and the complexity of the material. Many facilitators found that the structure of the course they facilitated played a significant role in making the topic accessible. However, some facilitators noted that certain topics remained challenging for participants with limited experience in the field. Despite these challenges, most participants found the training relevant, engaging, and beneficial.

One facilitator shared that their participants were early-career researchers with little or no prior knowledge of FAIR RDM. The course's structure, consisting of five sessions, allowed participants to gradually absorb the learning material and achieve the training program's objectives. The facilitator mentioned that a key strength of the course was how each session built upon the previous one, reinforcing the learning process and making the material more accessible (45). This approach helped participants with limited prior knowledge gradually grasp complex concepts. This suggests that the structured, progressive approach to delivering the content was an important factor in making the topic accessible to a broader audience.

Facilitators noted that topics which were new to participants were often more engaging and interesting. For example, some facilitators noted that their participants, who had little prior knowledge of their rights, found the training helpful in raising awareness (50). The positive reception was reflected in the active participation and questions posed by participants (74). This level of interest and engagement was echoed across several reports, as many facilitators found that participants, even without prior experience, were interested in the content (36-37, 42).

However, some facilitators highlighted challenges with the complexity of certain topics, particularly in technical areas like metadata systems, data repositories, and the differing templates and expectations across research-supporting organizations. These topics were difficult for some participants to fully understand (53-54). Facilitators pointed out that while the content was generally accessible, the volume of information presented in a short period of time made it hard for participants to keep up. This concern was mentioned by some facilitators who noted that participants found the material overwhelming (51-52, 53-54).

Despite these difficulties, the feedback from participants was generally positive from the facilitators' perspectives. Many facilitators reported that the topic was accessible, with most participants expressing satisfaction with the clarity and relevance of the content. Facilitators noted that the training helped make complex topics understandable, with participants finding the material directly applicable to their professional needs (90, 92).

Localisation of the content was another important factor that improved accessibility. One facilitator noted that providing training materials in both English and Hungarian allowed participants to share the content at their own institutions, further improving its accessibility (77-78, 79-80). This localisation was seen as particularly valuable, as it made the training more relevant and applicable in different regions.

The comparison between Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 revealed several key differences in how accessibility was addressed. In Cycle 1, prior knowledge played a larger role in making the material accessible, with participants often having some familiarity with relevant concepts. In contrast, Cycle 2 placed greater emphasis on a structured and progressive course design, which allowed participants, particularly those without prior knowledge, to gradually absorb the content. Another notable difference in Cycle 2 was the focus on localisation, as materials were provided in multiple languages to enhance accessibility, a feature not highlighted in Cycle 1. While Cycle 1 used scenario-based learning effectively, Cycle 2 incorporated more problem-based learning and group exercises, which were seen as helpful in enabling participants to apply the material practically.

5.4.2 Useful and difficult

Facilitators noted several aspects of their training experience that were both beneficial and challenging. The combination of lectures and practical exercises was very well received and helped participants to gain a better understanding of specific applications, such as the FAIR principles and concepts of research data management. Facilitators highlighted that problem-based learning assignments, in particular, allowed participants to integrate and apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts (45, 50, 64). Real-world examples were also considered valuable, as they helped participants relate the material to their professional environments (50, 93). The training materials were praised for being clear, well-structured, and up-to-date, providing a solid foundation for the sessions (56-57, 104).

Interactivity was another key strength. Facilitators observed that group work and peer-to-peer feedback encouraged active participation, fostering an open and collaborative atmosphere that supported deeper understanding (39-40, 120). Discussions and Q&A sessions also contributed to a more engaging learning environment, allowing participants to exchange ideas and clarify concepts (45, 50, 120).

However, facilitators faced some challenges in implementing certain aspects of the training. Time constraints were a recurring issue, with facilitators finding it difficult to allocate enough time for activities such as PBL tasks and case studies (61, 64, 120). This often resulted in a rushed delivery, which limited the depth of the learning experience. Additionally, simplifying complex topics, such as research integrity or legal issues, for a diverse audience was challenging without compromising scientific accuracy (144, 157).

Engagement also proved difficult at times. Some facilitators noted that certain participants were less active in discussions or group activities, leading to uneven participation (126, 134). This was particularly challenging in virtual sessions, where it was harder to create a sense of community and personal connection among participants (102, 104). Managing time during discussions also proved difficult, especially when addressing detailed or complex topics (156, 161).

We also broadly compared the facilitators' assessment to their reflections in Cycle 1. Both sets of feedback share similar themes, such as the importance of interactive exercises, the challenges related to time management, and the difficulties of engaging participants in online or hybrid formats. However, the feedback from the

current Learning Cycle 2 shows a greater emphasis on PBL tasks and group work as central methods for learning.

5.4.3 Participant Engagement

Most facilitators reported high levels of active participant engagement, particularly during interactive activities and discussions. PBL tasks were particularly effective, as it required participants to work in small groups. More experienced participants often assumed leadership roles within these groups, guiding others. One facilitator highlighted, „There was active participation from all participants, as documented by the completion of PBL assignments, active engagement in polls, and their dynamic presence in open discussions” (45). Small group activities, such as completing the research data management plan, facilitated this deeper engagement, while role-playing activities, such as participants taking on roles of „expert” or „journalist,” further encouraged interaction (60).

Peer-to-peer feedback also contributed to active participation. Facilitators observed that participants were engaged in providing and receiving feedback, with one stating, „They all had to work and provide peer-to-peer feedback” (59). Enthusiastic participation was also noted during open discussions, where participants shared experiences and asked questions (65, 64).

However, some facilitators observed reduced engagement during webinars, where the Q&A format was the primary method of interaction. In these sessions, participants tended to ask and answer questions, but more dynamic forms of interaction were limited. As one facilitator noted, „Since it was a webinar, it was not fully active but they were included in the Q&A format” (50). This format constrained deeper discussions, and some facilitators reported that opportunities for substantial dialogue were lost due to time limitations and the format itself (148, 135).

Participants were most engaged when the topics were personally relevant or resonated emotionally. Facilitators highlighted that when the content connected to participants’ real-world experiences, it led to more active participation and internal reflection. For instance, one facilitator observed, „The personal and emotionally resonant topic prompted internal reflection and informal peer discussion” (157). Topics such as gender equality, particularly when discussed in relation to participants’ own academic environments, prompted significant engagement and contributions. As one facilitator noted, „The gender equality component resonated particularly strongly given Italy’s ongoing challenges with gender parity in research and higher education” (131).

On the other hand, in larger or more formal settings, engagement tended to be uneven. In some sessions, a small group of participants dominated the discussions, while others remained less active. This was reflected in the observation, „Participants were generally quite engaged, although participation was somewhat uneven, with a smaller group contributing more actively than others” (159). Despite this, structured activities such as PBL assignments and peer feedback ensured that engagement remained high across the group, allowing for continued interaction and participation.

In comparison to Cycle 1, Cycle 2 showed improvements in webinar engagement and handling technical difficulties. While Cycle 1 faced challenges such as participants not

interacting during webinars and technical issues in hybrid settings, Cycle 2 saw better use of Q&A formats and more structured opportunities for interaction. Although uneven participation in large groups and some hybrid interaction difficulties persisted, the engagement in small group activities, particularly during PBL tasks, remained strong in both cycles. Additionally, the focus on personally relevant and emotionally resonant topics, such as gender equality, continued to drive higher engagement in both cycles, indicating a successful strategy for fostering participant involvement.

5.4.4 Tools performance

The analysis of how digital tools used as part of training delivery performed reveals several critical points. Generally, the tools used performed well, with Zoom polls being the preferred tool to minimise the need for multiple platform connections in online settings, ensuring smoother participation. Feedback from facilitators further highlighted the effectiveness of OpenPlato, with one for instance reporting, „OpenPlato platform worked well overall. Most participants reported little or no difficulty accessing or navigating the course content“ (160, 163).

However, issues with the Projects platform were repeatedly mentioned by training facilitators. Several facilitators reported difficulties with registration and access (36-37, 42, 43-44, 46-47, 48-49, 98). In addition, the platform was not that effective as a collaborative tool, as many participants did not engage with it as expected. One facilitator reported, „The Projects platform did not prove equally effective as a collaboration tool in terms of interaction and comment exchange“ (120). Technical issues with the Projects platform were also a recurring concern. One report described the platform becoming unavailable after a certain number of users registered: „Projects platform became unavailable after a certain number of users registered, likely due to scalability or server capacity limitations“ (43-44). Similarly, another issue arose when access was interrupted during peak use: „Projects platform’s access was interrupted for participants during peak use“ (46-47).

OpenPlato, in contrast, was recognised as a satisfactory self-paced learning tool, with positive feedback on its content and usability (22). However, some reports highlighted that OpenPlato was not ideal for live presentations, and a more traditional slide-based format was deemed more effective for in-session learning.

Furthermore, the Miro platform, designed to enhance interactivity (also for participant evaluation), faced significant challenges. One facilitator stated, „The Miro platform did not gain the participants’ trust. It proved difficult to use as it requires prior familiarisation, a minimum screen size, and a stable internet connection“ (45). This indicates that technical barriers and unfamiliarity with Miro contributed to its underperformance, suggesting it should not be deployed in all settings or for all participant groups.

Although these challenges arose, the tools still proved to be functional and valuable. For example, one facilitator mentioned, „We were able to use the Projects platform, and the students had access to the research data management plans uploaded there“ (51-52). Thus, in this instance, the platform worked well as a central hub for course materials but did not extend well to collaboration, a critical component of interactive learning. However, some facilitators noted the platform’s potential. As one facilitator

concluded, „The project platform can be developed further and more information about its use can be shared“ (121,122).

In Cycle 1, the Projects platform was mainly used for content sharing but faced issues with navigation, lack of a search index, and underutilized interactive features. Several trainers reported challenges with enrolment and tool integration, and some opted for face-to-face methods or email distribution instead of using digital tools. In Cycle 2, some similar issues with the Projects platform's interactive features were experienced, but there were fewer reports of enrolment problems. The OpenPlato platform saw a more positive reception in Cycle 2, with participants generally finding it easy to use. Additionally, in Cycle 2, there was a shift towards using Zoom polls to reduce reliance on multiple platforms, a change that was not present in Cycle 1. Overall, while some technical challenges remained in Cycle 2, there seemed to be improvements in usability and engagement compared to Cycle 1.

5.4.5 Uncertainties

The reports revealed several uncertainties and challenges that impacted participant engagement and understanding from the facilitators' perspectives. Some participants expressed difficulty understanding technical terms such as „metadata schemas“ and „Knowledge Organisation Systems“ (45). These terms were particularly challenging for participants with no prior exposure to the concepts, which led to confusion.

The Projects platform was mentioned again, whereby facilitators reported that it posed challenges for some participants, with issues such as registering in the wrong directory (48-49). Additionally, participants found the platform difficult to navigate (53-54), and it was noted that the platform crashed after a certain number of users had registered, likely due to scalability or server capacity issues (39-40). These issues affected the participants' experience and limited the smooth execution of the training activities.

Time constraints were also highlighted as a challenge. Some facilitators observed that participants did not have enough time to complete the PBL assignments fully, which was seen as indicative of gaps in understanding the material (64). Additionally, the time constraints seemed to affect the depth of the discussions, which left some participants feeling that they did not have sufficient time to engage with the content meaningfully.

In the online format, not being able to see participants' reactions or body language was identified as a challenge by facilitators (50, 55). This limitation reduced the level of interactivity, making it difficult for facilitators to gauge participant engagement or provide real-time adjustments based on the participants' needs.

The reports noted that some participants felt insecure, particularly when dealing with complex or unfamiliar topics. This insecurity was mentioned as potentially limiting their engagement, with some participants hesitating to ask questions or express doubts (66-69). This was an observation reported by the facilitators, and it suggests that the complexity of certain topics may have affected some participants' willingness to engage fully.

Uncertainty around the concept of open peer review was also noted, as some participants were unfamiliar with the process (65). This unfamiliarity led to confusion and hesitation in engaging with this part of the training, which suggests a need for clearer explanations or introductory materials on such topics in the future.

Several logistical challenges were mentioned during the training, including delays in receiving confirmation emails during the LPI platform registration process (98), which affected participants' ability to access the training materials on time. This delay was particularly problematic for participants who had not registered properly or were unable to access the case studies (146).

Some participants found the volume of content to be overwhelming, which affected their ability to stay engaged. The facilitator observed that limiting the theoretical content meant sacrificing the opportunity to address broader issues in science communication (58). This trade-off between content broadness and participant engagement suggests that some participants may have felt overloaded with material.

Finally, some participants experienced difficulties in shifting perspectives, particularly during discussions on personal versus systemic challenges within academia (157). These challenges were linked to differences in how participants viewed their roles in the academic system, which led to varying levels of engagement in these discussions.

The comparison between Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 reveals that some uncertainties persisted between the two cycles. In both cycles, participants struggled with technical terminology, particularly around specialised concepts. Similarly, the use of collaborative tools remained uncertain, as participants in both cycles did not fully engage with the tools provided. Time constraints continued to be a challenge in both cycles, with the balance between theoretical content and practical application remaining difficult to manage. While technical issues such as platform navigation were reported in Cycle 1, these did not emerge as significant concerns in Cycle 2, suggesting some improvements in technical support. However, key uncertainties regarding content complexity, tool usage, and time management were consistent across both cycles.

5.4.6 Additional Training Evaluation

Overall, 21 facilitator templates reported to have used additional evaluation instruments, of which they were asked to briefly describe the results. These evaluations were typically conducted through Zoom polls, Slido, or informal post-session feedback. The results from these evaluations were overwhelmingly positive, with participants rating their satisfaction between 4 and 5 on a 5-point scale in most cases. For example, in one case, 67% of participants rated the session as „5“ (most satisfied) and 33% as „4“ (64). Similarly, an evaluation from another session showed an average satisfaction score of 4.5 out of 5, with 47% of participants rating 4/5 and 53% rating 5/5 (92). In yet another instance, an evaluation revealed that 47% of participants rated the session 4/5 and 47% rated it 5/5, reinforcing the overall positive feedback from participants (161). This high satisfaction was consistently reflected in other sessions as well, with many participants commenting positively on the material's relevance and usefulness and appreciating the opportunity to learn new concepts.

Feedback from the training sessions highlighted some areas for improvement. Some participants felt that the training covered too many topics, which left them feeling overwhelmed by the volume of information. This concern was reflected in evaluations where participants noted that the broadness of content made it difficult to fully absorb key concepts (45, 64). While the quality of the content was generally appreciated, the delivery format, particularly the webinar format, was seen as a limitation. Some participants reported having little opportunity to actively engage or apply the material during the sessions, which affected the overall interactivity of the training (50, 63).

Despite these concerns, most of the feedback indicated that participants found the training valuable and relevant, particularly when it included practical and contextual examples.

5.5 Interviews with programme chairs, training facilitators, and coordinators

In the interviews, a broad range of topics and insights emerged, ranging from institutional strategies for implementing trainings to observed outcomes as a result of conducting training activities to barriers and challenges, success factors, experiences with the PATTERN platforms and future avenues for Open RRI trainings. In this section, we present a detailed description of our findings, following the topical sequence of our interview guideline.

We first asked interview partners to describe and summarise the main PATTERN activities carried out at their institutions. This question served both to introduce the interview topic and to encourage participants to recall and reflect on their work. Interview partners focused on three areas: designing trainings including tools and materials, piloting trainings, and outreach and exploitation. In line with their role outlined in the DoA, only thematic leaders reported work related to training design, which involved integrating project-based learning into the training approach and developing e-learning materials for the OpenPlato platform. Piloting and implementing trainings across various thematic areas formed a central part of PATTERN's work.

Five interview partners also highlighted outreach and exploitation as key activities. Their outreach efforts aimed to reach broad audiences, identify interested communities, and promote PATTERN's training offers across the research community. Several partners implemented accessible trainings such as webinars, which proved easier to distribute and lowered participation barriers. Partners also mentioned translating course materials to address local needs and publishing training resources on Zenodo to ensure broad accessibility.

5.5.1 Strategies for Implementing and Integrating PATTERN trainings

To understand how participating institutions embedded PATTERN trainings within their specific contexts and to identify lessons for future projects, we asked partners to describe their implementation approaches. Based on their accounts, we identified four main strategies, with many organisations combining more than one approach. This variety of integration strategies also reflects the diversity of institutional contexts of PATTERN organisations. The four strategies emerging from the interviews were:

1. Offering trainings at their own institution, integrated into existing curricula.
2. Offering trainings at their own institution, outside formal curricula.
3. Collaborating with other departments or institutions to deliver trainings.
4. Offering trainings beyond their own institution.

Four interview partners reported integrating PATTERN modules into existing curricula at their institution. This included incorporating them into optional PhD courses, mandatory courses for bachelor's and master's students, and mandatory PhD trainings:

„We were able to implement specific in person courses for PhD students, which we have integrated within the curriculum as elective courses.” (IP 1)

„We have classes about this and we integrate it to these classes. So our students need to get involved in this subject and we make it, we refurnished it which it as the partner wants actually. So we make it as a curricula [...]” (IP 9)

As one partner noted, this integration enabled them to offer ECTS credits as an incentive for student participation. However, this approach required adapting materials in collaboration with university representatives to meet institutional and curricular needs, resulting in a need for adaptation and the potential for tensions between project needs and institutional needs:

„So we said what if you know we adapted, we adapt these courses into you know what you require the students to have as competencies as part of your curriculum, [...] we have changed it a bit to actually fulfil the requirements of the of the whole curriculum” (IP 6)

Importantly, this strategy primarily attracted students rather than target groups such as senior researchers, data stewards, or librarians, raising questions about whether curriculum integration, while institutionally sustainable, may miss other audiences in need of Open RRI training.

Five partners described offering PATTERN trainings within their institutions without embedding them in existing programmes or curricula. This included organising trainings as one-off events, webinars, disseminating trainings organised by partners, and offering extracurricular training opportunities:

„Other trainings were offered also as extracurricular activities. Those that were open to the wider units are, yeah, [institution’s] research community.” (IP 1)

To reach participants, interview partners often invested considerable effort in engaging potential audiences, for example by contacting researchers directly in their laboratories.

„We organise some events inside of our library or we try to be strongly connected with them in their laboratories” (IP 2)

The comparison between those institutional approaches integrating trainings in curricula and those who did not also reveals a challenge for projects like PATTERN: integration can make projects more sustainable but limits the flexibility of implementation and diverse of target groups, while non-integration may demand more intense efforts for recruitment and engagement of potential participants.

A third approach, mentioned by three interview partners, involved collaboration for the delivery of trainings. This included partnerships with other departments at their own institution, such as PhD offices or libraries, as well as external collaborations with organisations like national libraries.

„So we teamed up with the library and we organised two citizens, one date citizen science workshops aimed at all kinds of organisations and companies” (IP 10)

„We focus on direct communication with academic libraries in academic institutions. So for your information, every academic library in [country] has a person, has a representative person, the contact person for open science issues. So we were staying close with these persons during the pilot implementations.” (IP 2)

Finally, three interview partners reported offering trainings outside their own institutions at festivals, conferences, and other public events, or by invitation from partner organisations, focusing on reaching researchers and professionals beyond their own institutional context. These activities allowed PATTERN to reach broader target groups beyond the immediate academic environment, potentially even engaging audiences not reached through conventional channels.

„We have also tried to organise hand son sessions in open science promotion events.” (IP 2)

„It was pattern but also it was [institution] reaching out to the [country's] community and saying we're doing this training. So come and come and do the training with us.” (IP 8)

5.5.2 What were your motivations for implementing the PATTERN trainings?

When asked about their motivations for joining the PATTERN project, interview partners revealed four main themes driving their participation. We were interested in these motivations to better understand how the PATTERN partners approached training implementation and which outcomes they may have prioritized or preferred. Moreover, these motivations might also reveal the potential a project like PATTERN offers over existing structured and programmes.

Working on developing, providing and sharing open RRI trainings emerged as the primary motivation, mentioned by seven interview partners. This corresponded directly to one of PATTERN's key objectives and encompassed several aspects.

„They were creating materials and then more or less keeping them to themselves and not sharing them for reuse. So the idea of creating materials that could be widely reused was quite exciting” (IP 8)

Partners expressed interest in realising their pedagogical interests, addressing perceived needs for comprehensive publicly available trainings, developing new training offers, including new topics in their teaching, improving their teaching with new materials, linking different transversal skills, and creating materials usable within their own institutional frameworks. One partner specifically mentioned the importance of sharing and promoting reuse of PATTERN training materials beyond the project. This focus on training development suggests that many partners saw PATTERN as filling a gap in available resources, whether because existing materials were outdated, inaccessible, or simply non-existent for certain topics.

„So I think one thing that appealed to me at that stage is that to have a comprehensive and publicly available set of training materials would be really useful because I think now trainers and data stewards are recognising how important it is to have fair training materials.” (IP 8)

„Yeah, I think we had two motivations. I mean, first of all to sort of to expand or how do you say it to make our own teaching a little bit more interesting and lively to the students.” (IP 10)

The second main motivation, expressed by six interview partners, centred on improving research culture at their own institutions. For these partners, improving

research culture meant increasing the visibility, recognition and presence of open RRI topics within their institutions, fostering responsibility and cultural openness, securing institutional commitment, and establishing open RRI as an integral part of researcher training.

„Also fostering a lasting cultural openness and responsibility.” (IP 1)

„And then also to strengthen the visibility of citizen science, science communication, research integrity, open RRI in general at the institution. So I think by having these training activities, not only for students, but also for researchers helped us to gain more visibility and recognition of these topics at the institution.” (IP 10)

Beyond institutional culture, four interview partners also emphasised targeting researchers at their institution at an individual level. They viewed PATTERN as a way to raise awareness among researchers and change their behaviour and practices through training offers that provided concrete tools and transferable skills. One interview partner explicitly noted that the PATTERN training framework showed potential as bridge between institutional and everyday requirements: *„And also we, by adopting this part and training modules we aim to create a more coherent sustainable Training framework that yeah, that bridges the institutional policies and everyday research practise.” (IP 1)*. This motivation reveals a gap in existing institutional contexts, whereby partners hoped that PATTERN could help close this gap. For one interview partner, this motivation also included leveraging momentum from previous projects on similar topics by continuing activities within PATTERN, suggesting that sustained effort over multiple projects might be necessary to achieve lasting impacts.

The third motivation, mentioned by four interview partners, involved improving their institution’s standing in the field of Open RRI. This meant positioning their institution as having expertise in open RRI, demonstrating alignment with research priorities and principles, sustaining and expanding networks in the field, and building synergies with other initiatives. Thus, being seen as a leader in fields like open RRI was a key interest in joining PATTERN.

„I mean we wanted also to show to [institution’s] community through the pattern project that we have developed a strong expertise in the [thematic area] field.” (IP 3)

„I mean, for the [thematic area] module, you can say that it’s it’s also strengthening the network that we have already in [thematic area]. So this gives us a new on an extra opportunity to get together and network with the people who are already involved because we don’t meet up so often.” (IP 10)

The fourth motivation, voiced by four interview partners, centred on hopes for systemic change and policy impact. These partners expected to influence systemic challenges in academia and the wider research community, increase open RRI presence in their countries, particularly where this topic remained novel, influence national research areas, and build research communities.

„So we want to foster this was we want to change research behaviour in our research community or in general in our research area in Greece, so programmes like pattern, I think it’s a good step for us to, to beginning to change this, this, this landscape.” (IP 2)

„The content of the pattern was very new for my institution. Also it was very new for my country too.” (IP 7)

„I’m always a bit hesitant because I would really like to blame the system and in training individual PhD candidates it’s almost like saying hey, it’s this is your fault and now you can do something about it. But we at least aim to give them a sense that they are not alone, and that by forming these kind of communities, we might be able to change the context eventually.” (IP 4)

This motivation extended beyond institutional or project boundaries, suggesting that some partners hoped that PATTERN could act as a driver for change in how research is conducted and evaluated.

5.5.3 Outcomes and Changes Observed by Interview Partners

Observed outcomes and changes as a result of implementing PATTERN activities is a key part of the evaluation and therefore, also formed the core of the interviews. We identified outcomes observed by interview partners across four main themes: benefits for the project team, changes in training participants, institutional changes, and wider outreach. The multi-faceted nature of the observed outcomes suggests that training projects can generate benefits beyond their immediate participants, though in the case of PATTERN, these benefits are unevenly distributed across organisations.

Two interview partners from thematic leader organisations described positive changes occurring within their project teams. Accordingly, participating in PATTERN had been an enriching experience that provided new learnings and, for one partner, expanded professional networks.

„And it helps individually, I think for people within the [institution’s] team like myself and [colleague], we’ve made quite a few contacts through the pilots that you know, on LinkedIn and things like that.” (IP 8)

„Also at personal level, yes, also these exchanges we had with these professors [...] was also nice for us to, you know, to meet her, to try to together, develop the concept of the training to try to define what would have been of interest of our researchers. But yeah, it was enriching for everybody, I think, yes.” (IP 1)

Although these team-level benefits were not primary project goals, they represent welcome spillover effects that will likely improve capacity for future training and EU-project work.

The second theme covers observed changes among training participants, which were reported by eight interview partners (only IP4 and IP10 did not report this). These included changes in awareness and attitudes, with six partners reporting observations like increased interest in open RRI topics and related careers, greater awareness of relevant skills, and high engagement levels attracting many participants.

„We can say that we have observed the growing interest in this topic among our researchers.” (IP 1)

„What has change in my institution, for example, number of graduate students, Phd students also, even faculty members increase their awareness about this subject.” (IP 7)

Five partners noted changes in learning outcomes, including increased learning, new perspectives, improved knowledge, and skills in handling PATTERN platform tools. One partner observed that PATTERN trainings fitted well with participants' current needs. Two partners mentioned skills changes, with one noting that participants valued data skills more highly after training, while another reported improved support and transferable skills for early career researchers. One interview partner observed behaviour changes, noting that PATTERN supported researchers in putting awareness into action and integrating open RRI into everyday practices. However, one interview partner expressed uncertainty about whether awareness had genuinely increased, mentioning that the trainings were *„an attempt to stress the importance of this topic, but I'm not sure we managed actually to”* (IP 3). The predominance of awareness and attitude changes over behaviour changes suggests that trainings could influence perspectives about open RRI but not necessarily translate directly into changed practices.

Seven interview partners reported about the extent to which they had observed institutional changes, though these varied considerably. Four interview partners explicitly mentioned little or no institutional change:

„I think it's a longer process and I think these trainings are part of a wider process but to be honest, we've had the, it's been quite hard for us to find sort of an institutional base you could say for [thematic area]” (IP 10)

„I think that they accepted the idea of training the students in [thematic area]. That was a good thing, but it's too much to say that we received, we create an institutional change.” (IP 3)

They saw limited influence on research culture or systemic change, observed no changes in institutional policies, and noted that many colleagues could not engage with PATTERN offers due to time constraints. One partner reported reduced impact because the training content did not fit well with existing institutional offers. Another expressed the lack of institutional change as senior researchers accepting the concept of open RRI but refraining from promoting it.

However, three interview partners reported to have observed institutional changes resulting from PATTERN. These included changes in policy and curricula, stronger governance sensitivity, integration of open RRI into institutional policies, commitments from institutional leaders to support open RRI, emerging discussions about formalising open RRI, and management interest in adding PATTERN trainings to official curricula.

„And yeah, open science, responsible research and innovation are becoming integrated into our policies, institutional policies and also everyday practises” (IP 1)

Four partners reported that their institutions increased their capacity, competence and expertise in open RRI. One partner mentioned that participating in PATTERN improved their institution's reputation and standing. The variation in institutional outcomes suggests that organisational contexts, pre-existing attitudes towards open

RRI, and power structures may be as important as project or training design in determining whether training initiatives lead to change.

Six interview partners discussed outcomes extending beyond individual organisations. These included increased interest from civil society members in open RRI topics, distribution and reuse of training materials supported by Zenodo, establishment or expansion of networks, reaching broad audiences, and starting new collaborations. One partner emphasised that PATTERN training materials informed development of a new national curriculum beyond their own organisation. These wider impacts indicate that project outputs can achieve reach beyond the original partner institutions, especially with well-planned dissemination strategies and openly available resources.

5.5.4 Barriers and Challenges

All interview partners described barriers and challenges, which we organised into seven themes encompassing training design and development; training delivery; participant recruitment and engagement; internal project collaboration; available resources; institutional factors; and sharing and exploitation. The prevalence of challenges across various aspects of the project suggests that implementing open RRI trainings in diverse and international institutional contexts are inevitable; yet, understanding these barriers can inform the design of future projects and support sustainability of PATTERN activities.

Three interview partners discussed challenges related to training design. One conceptual challenge involved designing trainings that covered PATTERN's broad open RRI thematic areas while remaining sufficiently in-depth. Two partners described challenges in project-internal collaboration during the development of training modules. Due to staffing fluctuations in one organisation, other partners perceived a lack of coordination, leadership, guidance on length and pedagogy, and early discussions among partners. This resulted in one partner experiencing a misfit between project plans and their activities, while another noted that they lacked formal pre-assessment to understand target group needs and that partners working on similar topics had diverging target groups. These challenges may be due to the comprehensive nature of PATTERN, with partners from different institutional and disciplinary backgrounds.

„I don't know something that I have been missing in general within PATTERN [...] is in a way especially for the development of courses, a stronger leadership, stronger guidelines on which kind of courses we should have developed, you know, for example, everybody did something different in terms of length, in terms of approach. I think it there were a lot of knowledge within the project also in term of pedagogical approaches for example.” (IP 3)

Eight interview partners described barriers related to training delivery. Some challenges were pedagogical and organisational. One partner struggled with covering too many topics in available sessions. Two partners mentioned challenges in organising online versus in-person formats, observing that in-person events proved more useful and effective but online trainings were necessary to reach more participants and meet the project KPIs: *„So also if I am looking at the result of the events in person or online events: in person events, maybe three or four times more*

effective and more useful for the people” (IP 7). One partner reported technical barriers in hybrid trainings. Four partners described challenges implementing the project-based learning approach, ranging from technical difficulties with PATTERN tools to feeling unable to implement this pedagogical approach due to its demands, to seeing no added value over other approaches.

„So we spent a lot of time like trying to find things to talk about when people were eager to learn, and this was also my weakness as a facilitator, since I was not so well, I didn't know so much about the topic, but we were supposed to discuss the cases ...” (IP 5)

One partner noted that project-based learning lacked flexibility, could not teach all skills, did not fit all topics, and did not appeal to diverse audiences from students to senior researchers. The resistance to project-based learning, despite its prominence in the PATTERN project's design, suggests that pedagogical approaches developed at project level may not translate easily into all delivery contexts or suit all target groups. Three interviews revealed challenges in project-internal coordination, with partners perceiving a lack of guidance for pilot plans and difficulties organising joint trainings due to differing target group demands and responsibilities.

Five interview partners mentioned difficulties in recruiting and engaging participants. Engaging researchers proved challenging, sometimes resulting in low participant numbers, with fewer attending than registered. As one partner outlined, targeted participants lacked time and resources to attend PATTERN trainings. One partner emphasised the need for continuous rather than one-off promotion, which itself presented challenges. This recruitment challenge points to a broader issue: open RRI trainings compete for attention with numerous other demands on researchers' time, and without institutional incentives or mandates, even well-designed trainings may struggle to attract participants. As IP 10 describes: *„And of course, whether that's due to a lack of interest or whether it's simply because researchers think that they already have enough on their plate, that's hard to say, but at least you can say that that part was difficult.”*

Four interviews highlighted the challenge of diverse target groups requiring different tailoring of contents and formats.

„But one of the difficulties or the feedback we had on our courses is that it's a bit difficult to match all the levels of awareness that the students have, because maybe we had some students who never thought about [thematic area] before and others who actually were more aware of the role in the society and came with stronger positions and thoughts.” (IP 3)

„And this is a little bit difficult sometimes, so we need to monitor participants from the previous pilots, in order to adapt again and again the training materials or the methods that we use to deliver our trainings.” (IP 2)

Accommodating varying needs and experience levels in the same training proved difficult, with researchers showing different preferences for content and interactivity. Addressing this diversity, as one partner noted, would require continuous adaptation of training content, materials and formats. One partner highlighted a related challenge where their target audience of researchers showed less interest than data

stewards, who were easier to engage but not the primary audience. One partner mentioned difficulty sustaining participant interest beyond trainings.

Three interviews revealed general collaboration challenges within PATTERN, beyond challenges in coordinating training development. These included task responsibilities and alignment, with too little interconnection in ongoing work, confusion about partner roles, challenging staff fluctuations, and decisions made without proper guidance. Communication with other partners emerged as a challenge for three interview partners, sometimes perceived as unclear or involving miscommunication. Two partners mentioned challenges in coordinating the training pilots, particularly early in the project. Resistance from partners towards using digital tools was also noted. These collaboration challenges reflect the difficulties inherent in large multi-partner projects where partners have different organisational cultures, priorities, and working styles.

Five interview partners mentioned resource-related barriers. Five had issues with time and budget, preventing them from implementing all desired activities, collaborations and trainings. They experienced time constraints, could not target all potential participants, or received insufficient institutional resources to promote open RRI further. One partner reported too few personnel and insufficient staff training for PATTERN's complex activities. Another faced constraints in pursuing geographically distant opportunities within the project framework.

„So we wanted to go as far as possible we could for example, but we wish we could do more” (IP 2)

„From my point of view, many libraries are working with limited staff capacity, not only capacity in terms of number of people that work, but skills capacity, so existing staff. Already, we had the main responsibilities to do and in the recent years the usual work, the workload has increased significantly” (IP 2)

„But this would require some real decisions or resources from the part of our university and that is not there yet.” (IP 5)

„And yeah, and the problem is time, the time constraints I think.” (IP 3)

Four interview partners described institutional barriers. These included top-down administration posing barriers to adopting new practices, bureaucracy, and challenges in cross-departmental communication and knowledge exchange. IP 3 noted lack of support from senior researchers for students spending time on open RRI: *„We tried to work with the PIs because some of them are more sensitive to these topics, other are not and they don't think that the students can spend time on these kind of skills, on developing these kind of skills, but they have to focus on research. So it's not easy.”*

IP 3 also noted that their institution provided no incentives or endorsements for training attendance, hampering participant engagement: *„Now that I'm thinking about it, there was no real endorsement as [colleague] was saying from the top levels, even though they were not against it.”*

One partner detailed multiple reasons preventing integration of PATTERN trainings into their curriculum: institutions resist changing programmes developed over years,

difficulty integrating pilots into higher education programmes, insufficient resources for integration into existing courses, translation skills offered as additional courses, bureaucratic constraints, different curriculum levels preventing PhD attendance at master courses, curriculum focus differing from PATTERN focus, and logistical difficulties. These experiences also highlight how a project like PATTERN, even if it designs relevant materials and puts efforts into participant engagement, can reach its limits in complex institutional systems. Here, IP 3 shared negative experiences: „*I think that the most important reason to say from another perspective is this administrative culture, which complicates enormously the adoption of new, often automatic practises.*”

Three thematic leaders highlighted barriers related to sharing and exploitation. For one partner, challenges began early when no good way existed to promote or share available training materials. Publishing on Zenodo to promote reuse, index materials, and link them to PATTERN only became possible later. Another partner mentioned challenges in making training materials on sensitive issues like mental health publicly available. The third partner described lack of clarity in promoting exploitation of PATTERN trainings. These exploitation challenges reflect the difference between creating resources and ensuring they reach and benefit users.

5.5.5 Successes Factors Supporting Implementation

Although not explicitly asked, interview partners also described factors that, from their perspective, contributed to successful training implementation. These success factors, viewed alongside the barriers, provide practical guidance for future projects about conditions and practices that can support effective training implementation.

Five interview partners highlighted existing institutional support structures as crucial. One interview partner emphasised that communication with institutional management and leaders, and having good contacts with people in positions of power who provided implementation support, was a key success factor: „*One of the things in pilot is really, really important: communication with the management of the institution. You have to make this communications, otherwise it's not easy.*” (IP 7). Another reported that good existing connections and relationships within institutional networks were critical success factors. Similarly, another reported support from their research support unit. Sufficient resources and good collaboration within the PATTERN project team were also reported as important. The emphasis on pre-existing relationships and support structures suggests that project success depends not only on what happens within the project but also on the pre-existing institutional setting. Partners embedded in supportive institutional environments with strong networks found implementation easier than those who had to build relationships and credibility from scratch or were even hindered by their institution.

Several factors supporting success in participant engagement also emerged. Early and widespread communication proved important, particularly for training formats like webinars, while another partner emphasised that communication with participants should be personal. One partner noted that recruiting participants proved easier when they were already aware and sensitive to open RRI topics, highlighting the relevance of an institution's pre-existing research culture. This reinforces existing differences between institutions: those that had already promoted

awareness of open RRI found it easier to recruit participants than those introducing these topics for the first time. IP 10 mentioned that presenting PATTERN to students as part of a larger international network helped them feel part of something bigger: *„And I think they also appreciated that this is part of a European wide network, so they could see that you know what they were doing was kind of feeding into this larger consortium.”* IP 4 described an unconventional method for dealing with registered participants not attending: *„So what we’ve decided to do is to impose a registration fee, but the registration fee is actually used towards dinner, so people are not paying for the trainers or the trainings or whatever. But if they register for the event and it, it will be something like €50 or something in that order. When they register, they will get a full day of training for free and after they will get a dinner that’s worth €50 with which hopefully we get some kind of a buy in. So that the people who register will really show up for the event.”*

Four partners described success factors for training implementation. One highlighted the importance of interactive in-person trainings, while another noted that interactive trainings require more time, which might not suit all target groups. A third partner emphasised that structured training offers combined with flexible accessible opportunities worked best. Using local language to promote and deliver trainings made them more accessible to institutional audiences. Communicating training relevance and usefulness to participants was also highlighted:

„They need reasons to share their data, and for them, the goodness of their heart is not a reason. [...] we need to give them hands-on reasons on why they should share that. Like they ask: OK, so why should I do it? Like that’s one of the main questions. Why should I do it?” (IP 2)

One partner noted that offering lunch during long in-person trainings improved success: *„You provide the lunch for the people. It was a very nice lunch. It’s very affordable budget, but people really liked it, people felt they belong to this event. This event’s interesting, with them, taking care of them.”* (IP 7) These practical factors may be easy to implement but can potentially affect participant experience and engagement.

Two pilot organisation representatives highlighted that providing certification or credits such as ECTS could incentivise participation. Formally recognising training participation can thus be an important factor for participant engagement, particularly among students and early career researchers.

Three interview partners mentioned promoting training reusability as important, particularly in the project’s final phase. One partner wanted to use remaining project months to share PATTERN training materials within their institution as widely as possible. Another noted that adapting PATTERN materials to local needs was key to successful implementation. One partner described obtaining national accreditation for PATTERN training modules as a key success, with reusability emerging as important for project sustainability. The focus on reusability and accreditation suggests that partners were thinking beyond the project timeline about how to sustain and extend PATTERN’s impact.

5.5.6 Other trainings related to open science and RRI implemented before

Three interview partners indicated having previous experience with trainings addressing open RRI topics at their institutions, some similar to PATTERN's approach such as research integrity trainings. However, one partner highlighted that previous trainings were old-fashioned compared to PATTERN's offers. Two partners indicated that no previous open RRI trainings existed at their institution and they had never done anything like PATTERN before. This variation in previous experience echoes the findings that emerged previously, namely that some partners could draw from established foundations while others introduced entirely new topics and approaches to their institutions. Projects like PATTERN can benefit from accommodating partners at different stages of institutional readiness by providing different types of support to those establishing new offerings versus those improving existing ones.

5.5.7 Intended Use of OpenPlato and Projects platforms Beyond PATTERN

When examining partners' intentions regarding continued use of OpenPlato and Projects, a clearer pattern emerges by distinguishing between perceived satisfaction and willingness to continue. While both platforms are recognised as valuable components of the project, confidence levels regarding post-project adoption differ.

5.5.7.1 OpenPlato

Across interviews, OpenPlato is generally associated with moderate to high satisfaction and comparatively clear intentions for continued use. It is repeatedly described as structured, familiar, and pedagogically understandable.

A central factor appears to be familiarity with the Moodle-based environment. As IP 2 noted: „*Open Plato is a Moodle platform... it's more common to use.*” This alignment with widely used institutional learning systems reduces the threshold for integration and increases user confidence.

In addition, OpenPlato is framed as a practical solution for extending reach. IP 7 explained: „*We are going to direct the people... to Open Plato because it's not easy for us to reach everybody.*” Here, the platform's value lies in scalability and flexibility, particularly when in-person teaching capacity is limited.

Critical remarks about OpenPlato are comparatively limited and tend to be contextual rather than platform-specific. Reservations relate mainly to institutional cultures that prioritise face-to-face teaching or to the need to observe long-term effectiveness in practice. Importantly, statements about future use are generally expressed without hesitation.

Taken together, the data suggest that OpenPlato has achieved a level of institutional familiarity and functional clarity that supports continued use. While not described in enthusiastic terms, it is perceived as reliable, usable, and compatible with existing teaching routines, which strengthens confidence in its sustainability.

5.5.7.2 Projects

In contrast, satisfaction with the „Projects” platform appears more varied and frequently more tentative. The data show appreciation for its collaborative ambition and structural possibilities, yet also highlight implementation challenges that affect confidence in continued use.

Recurring concerns include limited interaction in practice, unclear pedagogical framing, the need for stronger onboarding, and uncertainty regarding administrative autonomy after project completion. Hesitation markers are more frequent in relation to Projects, with interviewees using expressions such as „*I don't know*,” „*probably not*,” or „*we'll see*.” These formulations indicate conditional rather than firm continuation intentions.

Despite the mixed assessments, the platform was not dismissed. IP 6 noted that users became more autonomous over time, suggesting that early resistance may be linked to initial unfamiliarity rather than structural limitations. In some contexts, Projects was recognised as a useful collaborative or documentation environment and functioned effectively as a supplementary tool within blended formats.

However, compared to OpenPlato, continued use of Projects appears more dependent on specific conditions: clarity of long-term governance, ease of administration, clearer pedagogical positioning, and stronger integration into local workflows. Confidence in sustainability therefore seems more closely tied to future refinements and institutional ownership.

5.5.8 Willingness to Continue Implementation of the PATTERN Trainings

Across all interviews, programme chairs expressed a clear willingness to continue engaging with the PATTERN training materials beyond the formal project period. Notably, no interviewee rejected the idea of further implementation. The overall tone was strongly affirmative, in some cases emphatically so. For example, IP 4 responded to the question of continuation with: „*That for sure. Yes, yes, yes.*” Similarly, IP 9 stated: „*Definitely, yeah, yes, definitely.*” These statements indicate a high level of perceived relevance and acceptance of the training content.

However, closer analysis reveals that continuation is rarely understood as a direct replication of the original project format. Instead, the dominant pattern across cases is adaptive reuse and contextual integration.

Many interviewees described plans to selectively reuse specific modules, exercises, or slides rather than implementing the full training package unchanged. IP 8 captured this pragmatic approach succinctly: „*You will see bits and bytes you could take and others you can't and you'd build your own activity then around it.*” Similarly, IP 10 emphasised that the modular design allows for flexible reuse of „*one slideshow or one of the exercises*,” depending on local needs.

In several cases (e.g., IP 6), the materials were described as benchmarking resources to inform the development of locally tailored formats. This suggests that sustainability

is conceptualised less as maintaining a fixed curriculum and more as drawing on a resource pool that can be adapted to institutional contexts.

A second dominant pattern concerns the integration of PATTERN elements into existing institutional structures. Rather than continuing the training as a stand-alone initiative, several interviewees emphasised curriculum integration as the preferred sustainability strategy. As IP 3 stated: „*What I hope is that we will continue, but through institutional integration... not just as a stand-alone programme.*” Similarly, IP 5 reported ongoing discussions with deans and senior leadership regarding embedding elements into formal curricula.

These statements indicate that long-term continuation is primarily framed as structural embedding within institutional routines rather than project-based extension.

A smaller group of interviewees demonstrated particularly strong commitment by expressing ambitions to scale the training beyond their own institutions. IP 7 reported receiving multiple requests from other institutions and described efforts to extend the training to different regions, stating: „*We are getting lots of requests.*” Likewise, IP 9 emphasised intentions to disseminate the PATTERN curriculum more broadly at the national level. While not universal, such expansion-oriented approaches represent the strongest form of ownership observed in the data.

Only a small number of interviewees expressed a more cautious stance. IP 3, for example, linked continuation to evaluation outcomes and participant uptake, noting: „*Maybe the results of the evaluation will tell us.*” This indicates that sustainability may depend on demonstrated demand and feasibility considerations. Importantly, however, even these cases did not reject continuation outright.

5.5.9 Access to New Networks and Partnerships Through PATTERN

The interviews reveal a differentiated picture regarding whether participation in PATTERN has led to new networks or partnerships. As the project was still ongoing at the time of the interviews and nearing completion, some developments may still evolve beyond the reporting period. While not all interviewees reported the creation of entirely new formal collaborations, most described either strengthened existing networks or increased visibility that resulted in follow-up opportunities.

A dominant pattern across interviews is that PATTERN enhanced institutional visibility and intensified engagement within pre-existing networks rather than creating entirely new partnerships.

IP 1 explicitly framed the effect in these terms, explaining that the project did not generate completely new collaborations but significantly increased visibility, credibility, and structured engagement within existing networks. The institution became more active in national and European citizen science contexts and more frequently included in joint initiatives. In this case, PATTERN appears to have functioned as a catalyst, consolidating and activating existing relational infrastructures.

Similarly, IP 4 described how the project increased visibility to such an extent that training requests emerged without active outreach efforts. As IP 4 stated: „*Clearly the PATTERN project has great visibility and we've been contacted through the PATTERN network for delivering our trainings.*” Here, the network effect translated into concrete opportunities to pilot and disseminate trainings.

Several interviewees reported tangible follow-up activities emerging from PATTERN connections. IP 10 described two „Circle U” pilot projects initiated through PATTERN-related contacts, involving additional European partners. Likewise, IP 9 linked PATTERN outputs to national EOSC-related competence centre initiatives, suggesting integration of PATTERN curricula into broader open science infrastructures. In these cases, participation in PATTERN appears to have supported strategic positioning within larger European research and training ecosystems.

IP 4 further reported that lessons learned from PATTERN are being integrated into a forthcoming doctoral network proposal, indicating that the project is already feeding into new funding-oriented collaborations even before its formal completion.

Beyond formal partnerships, several interviewees emphasised informal or local network expansion. IP 5 described establishing valuable contacts in one specific thematic field that would not otherwise have emerged, leading to reciprocal visits and workshop participation. Similarly, IP 10 highlighted an extension of local and national networks through project-related workshops.

These accounts suggest that PATTERN has generated relational capital even where formalised partnerships have not yet materialised.

Only one interviewee (IP 2) clearly indicated that, at the time of the interview, no new concrete partnerships had emerged. IP 2 reported that, despite initial follow-up contacts with research centres, these had not developed into formal partnerships at the time of the interview: „*Right now I wouldn't say yes.*” Given that the project was still ongoing at the time of the interviews, this assessment may reflect timing rather than absence of potential.

5.5.10 Access to New Infrastructures Through PATTERN

In contrast to the strong networking effects described above, access to new infrastructures through PATTERN was limited.

The dominant finding across interviews is that participation in the project did not provide access to major new institutional or European-level infrastructures. Several interviewees explicitly stated that no such access had emerged.

While some digital platforms were introduced within the project context, these were generally not perceived as structural infrastructural gains. In institutions with established internal systems, project platforms were considered supplementary rather than transformative. As IP 5 explained: „*It's easier to use whatever we have in house because we also have the user support.*”

Only one interviewee (IP 9) mentioned a concrete acquisition linked to PATTERN activities, referring to the purchase of a new notebook to support teaching: „*That’s the new infrastructure which we bought for this.*” However, this represents a local operational investment rather than access to broader infrastructures.

In some cases, interviewees did not report immediate funding gains but described emerging structural positioning that may lead to future funding opportunities.

IP 9, for example, linked PATTERN-related competence development to broader national infrastructure ambitions. The interviewee described efforts to consolidate open science and FAIR-related competencies at national level, with the expectation that this positioning could attract governmental funding support.

Although no concrete funding decision had materialised at the time of the interview, this statement reflects more than mere optimism. It indicates a strategic attempt to leverage PATTERN outputs—particularly competence development and curriculum consolidation—as part of a national funding narrative. In this case, PATTERN functions as a capacity-building instrument that may strengthen eligibility for public funding schemes rather than directly generating funding itself.

A similar forward-looking perspective was expressed by IP 5, who suggested that potential funding effects might only become visible after the project’s completion: „*We’ll see when the project ends.*” This highlights the temporal dimension of funding impacts, which often materialise after project closure rather than during implementation.

Taken together, these cases suggest that funding-related effects may be indirect, strategic, and medium-term rather than immediate.

5.5.11 Are the PATTERN Trainings an Effective Way for Universities to Address Open Science and RRI?

Across all interviews, the PATTERN trainings are assessed as a highly suitable instrument for addressing Open Science and RRI in higher education. Their perceived effectiveness rests on three closely connected dimensions: the translation of abstract principles into practice, their strategic value for institutions, and a structured yet adaptable design.

A central strength lies in the trainings’ capacity to translate normative frameworks into concrete research contexts. Interviewees repeatedly noted that Open Science and RRI are often perceived as abstract policy concepts; the PATTERN materials were valued for making them practical and operational. IP 9, for example, highlighted the relevance of the FAIR RDM components in relation to mandatory data management plans required by funding bodies. In this sense, the trainings equip participants with competencies that align directly with institutional and funding expectations at both national and European levels.

Interviewees also emphasised that strong materials alone do not automatically generate impact. IP 2 stressed that effectiveness depends on interactive facilitation, sufficient discussion time, and adaptation to disciplinary contexts rather than rigid,

standardised delivery. The materials were therefore perceived less as a fixed script and more as a structured framework that requires active moderation and contextualisation in order to be effective. As IP 2 summarised: „*The material is really adjustable and adaptable. So you can decide what you're going to put in, what you're going to take out and still have a flow.*”

Beyond their pedagogical value, the trainings were described as strategically significant. Several interviewees linked them to third mission objectives and to strengthening institutional visibility in Open Science and RRI. IP 10 argued that structured training programmes allow universities to demonstrate commitment and give these topics greater institutional „*weight.*” In this perspective, the trainings function not only as educational tools but as instruments of institutional legitimation and signalling, providing tangible evidence that competencies in Open Science and RRI are being systematically developed.

A further strength lies in the balance between a coherent framework and local flexibility. IP 10 described the trainings as „*tested*” and evidence-informed, highlighting the value of a structured European-level approach. Their modular design, however, allows institutions to adjust content to local priorities and disciplinary needs. This combination of structure and adaptability appears to be a key factor in their perceived suitability across diverse institutional contexts.

5.5.12 Looking Ahead: Development Priorities Identified by Interviewees

When invited to imagine a hypothetical five-year extension of PATTERN, interviewees used the question as a reflective exercise to articulate what they would strengthen, deepen, or adjust. Their responses highlight areas where they see further potential for development.

Several interviewees emphasised that lasting impact depends not only on high-quality content, but on sustained behavioural change. Rather than expanding the number of modules, they suggested strengthening mechanisms that support long-term adoption of Open Science and RRI practices.

IP 2 proposed engaging more explicitly with behavioural science perspectives to better understand how researchers change routines and decision-making processes. Similarly, IP 4 stressed the importance of building „enduring communities” around these topics, „because communities are always stronger than single individuals” (IP 4). The emphasis here lies on reinforcing practice, peer exchange, and continuity beyond individual training sessions.

Interviewees also pointed to thematic areas that are rapidly evolving and would merit stronger integration. Artificial intelligence and research security were mentioned repeatedly. IP 9 for instance highlighted that AI fundamentally reshapes research practice and introduces new integrity-related challenges: „So probably we need to somehow find the AI component of these topics, I mean you can write now a whole study with an AI, but it's not fair and within the Open Access lots of fraud about these topics, so that need to be highlighted for the students. So these are new topics which we can implement” (IP 9).

The reflections suggest that future training initiatives in this field would need to remain responsive to such developments and continuously update their content.

Another recurring theme concerned the structural recognition and presentation of the training offer. Participants highlighted the value of framing the curriculum as a coherent set of transferable skills that extend beyond academic contexts. As one participant (IP 5) noted, „That we recognise this set of skills that is actually... that comprises a whole and that is useful for, for also people outside academia.” In line with this, IP 5 suggested presenting the curriculum more systematically as a transferable skills package, potentially linked to ECTS credits or embedded within doctoral education structures. The underlying recommendation emphasises enhancing the visibility, coherence, and institutional anchoring of the training rather than expanding its content.

Finally, several interviewees indicated that implementation processes only began to stabilise toward the later stages of the project. IP 1 described the duration as „not enough”, noting that improvements became visible across learning cycles. Taken together, the reflections underline that meaningful institutional embedding requires time, iteration, and repeated implementation cycles before stable routines and quality improvements become visible.

6 Summary of Results

This section provides a summary of key findings derived from each evaluation instrument (see Figure 22), followed by targeted recommendations.

Summary of Evaluation Findings

Figure 22: Visualisation of key evaluation findings.

Overall, this report covers 150 trainings, of which 35 were delivered in Learning Cycle 1 of the PATTERN project, while 115 were implemented in Learning Cycle 2. The most common thematic area was FAIR data management, which appeared in nearly a third

of all trainings, followed by Open Access, Management and Leadership, and Citizen Science. Most trainings targeted beginners only or combined beginner and intermediate levels. Live in-person sessions were the most frequent format, though live online sessions were also common. Participants came from mixed disciplines in almost nine out of ten trainings, and their career backgrounds also varied widely. These figures show that PATTERN successfully reached a broad and diverse audience. The strong focus on FAIR data management and Open Access reflects the immediate practical needs of researchers, while the mix of disciplines and career stages suggests that open RRI topics appeal across the whole research community.

The **quantitative participant questionnaire** collected responses from 1,747 PATTERN training participants. Most respondents were women and on average 33 years old. Overall satisfaction of participants was extremely high, indicating general effectiveness of the PATTERN trainings across all thematic areas and target groups. We also compared groups on key evaluation dimensions and found minor differences. Accordingly, natural science participants rated the training slightly less favourably than those from other disciplines. Bachelor's students were a somewhat critical group, while master's students and senior scientists gave the most positive ratings. Women rated the training slightly higher than men on several points. Among thematic areas, FAIR data management, Open Access and Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion received the strongest scores, though differences were small. Online participants rated the training more favourably than those attending in person. Where the OpenPlato platform was used, evaluations were more positive, while the Projects platform was linked to higher active engagement but lower scores on other measures.

The **qualitative participant evaluation** within the PATTERN project showed that participants most enjoyed the interactive format of the trainings, including group activities, quizzes and breakout rooms. They also valued peer discussion, practical exercises and real-life examples, and the high quality and expertise of the trainers. The most common form of usefulness was gaining new knowledge, but this varied by career stage: early career researchers often encountered topics for the first time, while senior researchers updated existing knowledge. Librarians and support staff consistently described usefulness in terms of being better able to advise researchers. When asked about skills, many participants distinguished between gaining knowledge and developing a skill, noting that single sessions are better for raising awareness than for building fully consolidated competencies. Concrete skill gains were most clearly reported in FAIR data management (writing a data management plan, creating README files) and Open Access (selecting journals, detecting predatory publishers, managing copyright), while trainings Management and Leadership provided a sense of solidarity and shared struggle.

From a pedagogical perspective, **PATTERN facilitators** found that a structured, progressive course design helped make complex topics accessible, especially for participants with little prior knowledge. Problem-based learning and group exercises worked well, and participants engaged actively when topics felt personally relevant. However, time constraints were a recurring problem, sometimes forcing a rushed delivery. Webinars produced less dynamic engagement than smaller group formats. Furthermore, facilitators' experiences with digital tools were mixed: The OpenPlato platform performed reliably and was easy to use, while the Projects platform faced

registration problems and limited uptake as a collaboration tool. Miro proved difficult for participants who were not already familiar with it.

Facilitators recommended allocating more time for practical exercises, simplifying complex concepts, encouraging smaller discussion groups, and offering follow-up sessions. The facilitators' experiences show that effective teaching methods and well-organised training sessions are crucial. However, reported issues with Projects and Miro highlights that using new platforms without sufficient onboarding may introduce barriers.

The **qualitative interviews with PATTERN partners** provided an overarching, institutional perspective on PATTERN's impact. For offering trainings, institutions adopted four main strategies: integrating trainings into existing curricula, offering them outside formal curricula, collaborating with other departments or institutions, and delivering trainings beyond their own organisation. Partners observed strong changes for individual researchers' awareness and attitudes, in line with the results from the participant evaluation. Behavioural and institutional-level changes were less common. Partners also reported several barriers, which varied across institutions, but included difficulties in training design and delivery, especially with project-based learning, low researcher engagement due to time pressure, and limited resources. Success factors included strong institutional support, early personal communication with potential participants, interactive in-person formats, and offering certification or credits. Most partners intended to continue using PATTERN materials after the project, but not as a fixed curriculum. Instead, they planned to adapt modules selectively and integrate them into existing institutional courses. OpenPlato was seen as more sustainable because it resembles familiar learning platforms while the Projects platform received more cautious support. Overall, the PATTERN trainings were judged an effective way for universities to address open science and RRI because they turn abstract principles into practical, research-relevant skills. Looking ahead, partners wanted to focus more on lasting behavioural change and on building enduring communities around these topics.

In sum, the PATTERN project has successfully developed and piloted a comprehensive, multi-lingual, modular, and adaptive training programme addressing nine key topics in Open and Responsible Research and innovation across Europe. The evaluation shows that the PATTERN approach is highly effective in raising awareness, increasing interest, and providing practical, applicable knowledge in Open Science and RRI among different target groups – from students and researchers to data stewards and librarians. However, the evaluation also reveals challenges regarding skill development vs. knowledge increases, participant benefits and engagement across different groups - including disciplines, career stages, and topics, the role of digital platforms, and the challenges of achieving lasting institutional change in different organisational contexts.

7 Conclusions and Recommendations

Drawing from the extensive findings of the PATTERN training evaluation, this final section translates the most important results into a set of actionable recommendations and conclusions for different audiences: training facilitators, future training developers and programme designers, and OPEN RRI funders and policymakers.

7.1 Recommendations for trainers and facilitators

The following recommendations are based directly on feedback from training participants and facilitator reflections and are intended for those who plan on delivering PATTERN trainings or similar training offers in the future (see Figure 23).

Recommendations for trainers and facilitators

Figure 23: Visualisation of recommendations for trainers and facilitators.

Firstly, trainers should prioritise interactivity and practical applications of training contents. The most consistent finding across results from the different participant evaluation instruments is that participants highly value interactive, discussion-based, and hands-on formats. In contrast, passive or lecture-heavy trainings were perceived more negatively. More specifically, trainers should integrate quizzes, peer discussion, real-world case studies, and hands-on exercises as much as possible. Such activities require sufficient time; thus other contents might need to be reduced to accommodate them.

Secondly, trainers must distinguish clearly between awareness-raising and skill development. The evaluation highlights that single-session trainings are effective for generating awareness, knowledge, and interest but less suited for developing fully

consolidated, transferable skills. Trainers should be explicit with participants about this distinction, framing the training as an introduction or a tool for knowledge acquisition and awareness raising, to avoid disappointment. To promote skill development, if possible, trainers should design follow-up mechanisms, such as peer-learning communities, advanced workshops, or practical assignments that require application over time.

Thirdly, content and pedagogy of OPEN RRI trainings should be tailored to specific participant groups, as the evaluation revealed both statistically significant and qualitative differences in how different participant groups experienced the trainings. For bachelor's students, who were the most critical group and found the training less applicable, facilitators should consider adapting content to be more foundational, connecting it directly to other coursework such as writing a first thesis, or explicitly acknowledging that the concepts are for future application. For participants from the natural sciences, who rated the training less favourably across many dimensions, facilitators could use more examples, case studies, and disciplinary language specific to the natural sciences, avoiding a one-size-fits-all approach. Groups with mixed disciplines may require more extensive tailoring or even several different exercises adapted to each discipline in the group. For librarians and support staff, who consistently framed the training's usefulness in terms of their ability to advise researchers, trainers should offer specific tracks, examples, or breakout discussions focused on how this group can act as multipliers.

Fourthly, the evaluation results highlight the critical aspect of optimising format of the training – online vs. in-person – and the use of digital tools. Live online trainings were rated highly by participants and are an accessible, scalable option. However, they require practical and interactive elements to be successful, possibly more so than in-person trainings. In-person sessions were noted as being more effective by training facilitators, but this impression is not directly mirrored in the participant evaluation. Perhaps in-person trainings are particularly useful for promoting in-depth discussion, building community, or for target groups less accommodated with digital environments. The choice of digital platforms to support training delivery also plays a critical role. More importantly, training facilitators should not assume uniform levels of digital literacy or familiarity with digital tools among their participants and should provide a clear tutorial for any new platform.

Fifthly, time constraints must be addressed and managed proactively, to avoid that trainings are perceived as too dense or broad. If necessary, training facilitators should reduce the amount and scope of content, particularly in favour of interactive and practice parts. Providing reading materials before pre-session or one-page summaries in advance can free up session time for discussion and practice. If a topic is large, splitting it into multiple shorter sessions is another option to reduce density.

7.2 Recommendations for future training developers and programme designers

Experiences and evaluation findings from PATTERN also offer several strategic lessons and guidelines for those designing new training programmes or curricula in the area of Open Science and RRI.

Recommendations for future training developers and programme designers

Figure 24: Visualisation of recommendations for future training developers and programme designers.

Firstly, future programme developers should prioritise thematic areas with high perceived relevance to their target groups immediate professional needs, for example by matching interests and needs through an ex-ante needs survey. The evaluation showed that topics linked to concrete funder mandates (e.g. Horizon Europe) or daily tasks, such as FAIR Data Management, Open Access, and Gender and Inclusion, were rated most highly. Topics perceived as broader or less relevant to researchers' daily tasks, such as Science Communication or Research Integrity, tended to receive more mixed reviews. When developing new trainings, designers should frame the content in terms of its practical utility and alignment with existing obligations such as Horizon Europe requirements or national policies. For topics like Science Communication, the question of what is in it for the researcher must be explicitly addressed and answered. For broad topics whose scope is open-ended (e.g. Science Communication), programme developers should explicitly define and name the specific sub-aspects to be covered, so that relevance and scope are transparent to the target audience.

Secondly, training materials should be designed for sharing and adaptability. The most promising path to sustainability is creating a modular, adaptable resource pool – like PATTERN has done. Institutional representatives often indicated that after the project ended, they would use bits and pieces of PATTERN training materials integrated into their existing local courses. If sustainability is an objective, training developers should create content as self-contained modules that can be easily

combined and re-combined. Moreover, clear trainer guides should be provided on how to adapt and re-contextualise these modules for different disciplines, career stages, and institutional settings. This approach reduces dependency on the original developer and considerably promotes the potential for long-term reuse. Regarding sustainability, we found that curriculum integration emerged as promising avenue though, it should also be acknowledged that mechanisms that go beyond formal curricula – like communities of practice, train-the-trainer model, or institutional research support services (e.g. libraries, data stewards) can support institutional embedding and capacity building,

Thirdly, institutional barriers must be considered and addressed from the outset of any new training initiative. The interviews revealed that a lack of senior researcher support, bureaucratic hurdles, and the absence of incentives and formalisation like ECTS credits or certificates were important obstacles to implementation and uptake. The interviews also revealed that existing alliances with key decision-makers in the organisation, such as deans, and aligning training contents with institutional policies, such as a Gender Equality Plan or an Open Science mandate, can increase institutional support and through that, both relevance and uptake.

7.3 Recommendations for OPEN RRI funders and policymakers

The PATTERN project also provides valuable lessons for effectively funding and scaling capacity-building in Open Science and RRI, which can inform policymakers and funding bodies such as the European Commission.

Recommendations for OPEN RRI funders and policymakers

Figure 25: Visualisation of recommendations for OPEN RRI funders and policymakers.

Firstly, increasing efforts should be focussed on levers of institutional change rather than targeting primarily individual researchers. The evaluation results suggest that PATTERN was effective at raising awareness and changing attitudes in individual participants, while institutional change remained limited at most organisations. This is a structural reality that hampers large-scale change of research practices: trainings alone do not change institutions. Instead, the translation of individual learning into

broader research practices is supported by factors like institutional incentives, leadership support, and structural integration.

Secondly, the EU can leverage policy as a powerful driver for training uptake and changing research practices. The evaluation strongly indicated that training topics gained relevance for researchers when linked to mandatory requirements, such as Horizon Europe's Gender Equality Plan, funder-mandated Data Management Plans, or the ERA Act provisions on research integrity. The EU should maintain and strengthen policy requirements that require open and responsible practices, and where such policy mandates exist, funding for training should be explicitly linked to help researchers and institutions to comply with the requirements. This would support a cycle in which policy drives demand and training enables compliance and skill development.

Thirdly, policymakers should recognise the advantages of adaptability over rigid curricula. The PATTERN project's success and reach was supported by its development of a diverse ecosystem of materials and adaptations with its pool of tested, modular resources as key outcome. Evaluation criteria for such projects should therefore reward the creation of adaptable, re-usable, and well-documented training materials, not merely the number of pilots or participants. Furthermore, funding bodies should require a clear sustainability and exploitation plan focused on open licensing under licences such as Creative Commons Attribution and on integration into existing national or institutional training infrastructures.

Fourthly, the evaluation provided several future avenues that need to be considered in developing further thematic areas for researchers' training and for keeping up with changing landscapes in OPEN RRI. Artificial intelligence is already changing research practice and introducing new questions about integrity, authorship, and data use that none of the current PATTERN modules fully address. Furthermore, interview partners outlined a need to better understand how to foster enduring behavioural change and build enduring communities around Open RRI. Future funding calls should address these emerging issues to ensure that researchers are equipped to navigate these challenges. At the same time, the thematic areas addressed in PATTERN will continue to stay relevant, as ongoing developments like the European Open Science Cloud, the adoption of FAIR data practices, or current initiatives for reforming research assessment will likely increase demand for the competencies addressed in PATTERN.

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9 Appendix A: Short Participant Questionnaire

9.1 Introduction

Thank you for participating in the PATTERN training!

We would like to ask you some questions about your training experience. Completing the questionnaire will take approximately 5 minutes.

Your honest feedback allows us to improve and refine our trainings.

All your answers are anonymous and cannot be traced to you. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time. No personal identifying information will be collected. Your responses will be kept confidential. Aggregated responses will solely be used for research purposes and improvements of the training. By proceeding, you consent to participate in this survey. Thank you for your time.

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements about your training experience.

9.2 Response scale

Response scale:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable

9.3 Items

Items should be randomised (except for sociodemographics)

Questions about the content of the training

1. The training materials were clear.
2. The training materials were relevant and up to date.
3. It seemed to me that the training tried to cover too many topics.

Questions about the appropriateness of the training for its target group

4. The training taught me a lot of new concepts.
5. I managed to complete the requirements of the training without feeling unduly stressed.
6. The training provided sufficient flexibility for my personal learning needs.

Questions about presentation of materials and communication between training facilitators and participants

7. The training was well structured.
8. I was given the chance to actively engage during the training.
9. The aims and objectives of this training were NOT made very clear.
10. The online platforms used in the training were adequate tools for learning.

Questions about general perceptions of the training

11. During the training, my interest in the topic was increased.
12. Overall, the training experience was worthwhile.
13. Overall, I'm satisfied with the quality of this training.

Sociodemographic items

14. What is your age? (in years)
 - a. [open field]
15. What is your gender?
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Non-binary
 - d. Prefer not to say
 - e. Other: [open field]
16. What is your primary academic discipline or field of study?
 - a. Arts & Humanities (e.g., Literature, Philosophy)
 - b. Social Sciences (e.g., Sociology, Psychology)
 - c. Natural Sciences (e.g., Biology, Chemistry)
 - d. Engineering & Technology (e.g., Computer Science, Engineering)
 - e. Medical & Health Sciences (e.g., Medicine, Nursing)
 - f. Business & Economics (e.g., Business Administration, Economics)
 - g. Other: [open field]
17. What best describes your current academic or professional stage?
 - a. Bachelor's student
 - b. Master's student
 - c. Doctoral student or predoctoral researcher
 - d. Postdoctoral researcher
 - e. Senior scientist or Professor

10 Appendix B: Extended Participant Questionnaire

10.1 Introduction

Thank you for participating in the PATTERN training!

We would like to ask you some questions about your training experience. Completing the questionnaire will take approximately 5 minutes.

Your honest feedback allows us to improve and refine our trainings.

All your answers are anonymous and cannot be traced to you. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time. No personal identifying information will be collected. Your responses will be kept confidential. Aggregated responses will solely be used for research purposes and improvements of the training. By proceeding, you consent to participate in this survey. Thank you for your time.

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements about your training experience.

10.2 Response scale

Response scale:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	NA
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable

10.3 Items

Items should be randomised (except for sociodemographics)

Questions about the content of the training

- 18. The training materials were clear.
- 19. The training materials were relevant and up to date.
- 20. It seemed to me that the training tried to cover too many topics.

Questions about the appropriateness of the training for its target group

- 21. The training taught me a lot of new concepts.
- 22. I managed to complete the requirements of the training without feeling unduly stressed.
- 23. The training provided sufficient flexibility for my personal learning needs.

Questions about presentation of materials and communication between training facilitators and participants

- 24. The training was well structured.
- 25. I was given the chance to actively engage during the training.
- 26. The aims and objectives of this training were NOT made very clear.
- 27. The online platforms used in the training were adequate tools for learning.

Questions about general perceptions of the training

- 28. During the training, my interest in the topic was increased.
- 29. Overall, the training experience was worthwhile.
- 30. Overall, I'm satisfied with the quality of this training.

Questions adapted from Interactive evaluation activity

- 31. I enjoyed the training.
- 32. Which aspects of the training did you enjoy?
 - a. [open field]
- 33. The training was useful for me.
- 34. In what ways was the training useful to you?
 - a. [open field]
- 35. I could gain new skills.
- 36. Which skills did you gain?
 - a. [open field]
- 37. I will apply what I have learned in practice.
- 38. What specifically can you apply in practice?
 - a. [open field]

Sociodemographic items

- 39. What is your age? (in years)
 - a. [open field]
- 40. What is your gender?
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Non-binary
 - d. Prefer not to say
 - e. Other: [open field]
- 41. What is your primary academic discipline or field of study?
 - a. Arts & Humanities (e.g., Literature, Philosophy)
 - b. Social Sciences (e.g., Sociology, Psychology)
 - c. Natural Sciences (e.g., Biology, Chemistry)
 - d. Engineering & Technology (e.g., Computer Science, Engineering)
 - e. Medical & Health Sciences (e.g., Medicine, Nursing)
 - f. Business & Economics (e.g., Business Administration, Economics)
 - g. Other: [open field]
- 42. What best describes your current academic or professional stage?

- a. Bachelor's student
- b. Master's student
- c. Doctoral student or predoctoral researcher
- d. Postdoctoral researcher
- e. Senior scientist or Professor

11 Appendix C: Guideline and materials for interactive evaluation activity

This includes a how-to for the activity targeting facilitators and a template that can be used for implementing the activity. The template is provided in Miro (and on the PATTERN SharePoint as a print version) and can be used online or offline.

If you use the Miro board with your participants in an offline, in-person setting, make sure that participants have a computer for navigating the board, as using Miro on a phone can be challenging!

We provide an explanation of how to use an analogue version of the activity further below.

How-to implement the activity using an online Miro board?

The training facilitators are asked to use the **provided Miro board link**.

Find an empty frame (with no results in it) and name it:

Institution_Name of YOUR training activity_Date.

At the conclusion of your training activity, allocate a few minutes to share the Miro board link with your participants.

Click your frame and then share the Miro board link with your participants. By opening Miro, they land directly on the frame.

Allow your participants time to place the provided sticky notes along the sliders to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on the provided questions.

- I enjoyed the training - because of
- The training was useful for me - and why
- I could gain new skills - and which
- I will apply what I have learned in practice - in specific

Each participant places a sticky note on the slider according to their level of agreement or disagreement and writes a note or explanation on it. The entire group's results will be documented. This process can also be carried out in small groups.

Encourage participants to write any additional comments or information on the sticky notes if they wish, and welcome suggestions for improvement in the adjacent section of the board.

When participants are finished populating the board, you can ask them to further comment on what they wrote to facilitate a discussion between participants.

When the activity is completed and you are sure that no participant will add anything else, take screenshots for documentation. Then notify the ZSI team and we will archive the frame on a different board.

12 Appendix D: Facilitator template for reflection and documentation

This template provides instructions on how to document the interactive evaluation activity. It also provides space for reflections of facilitators on how they experienced the training.

Please complete the template in this online form: <https://forms.gle/s1qsuNY2mGHEaSlz6>

You can find an overview of the questions below but please use the online form for completing the template.

--

Dear training facilitator,

This template serves as a reporting tool for documenting your experiences and reflections on the PATTERN training activity you conducted. It is designed to gather information on each activity and contribute to the improvement of future activities. Effective documentation of activity results is essential for the evaluation process. With it, the ZSI team will be able to analyse results and draw conclusions accurately.

We do not expect training facilitators to complete a documentation/reflection template for every session of a given training, once per training course is sufficient. Please ensure to document your activity concisely and clearly.

General Information

Please indicate your institution:	
Please indicate the name of your training (as published):	
Please indicate the date your training took place. (DD MM YY)	
Who is the main contact person?	
Indicate nr of corresponding row/ID in the Excel monitoring sheet (see here)	

Training approach

Item	Description
Please give a short summary of your training approach, including the	

pedagogic approach of your training.	
How and for which tasks did you use the Projects platform?	
How and for which tasks did you use the OpenPlato platform?	
Which activity/materials did you use?	
What was useful and beneficial?	
What was difficult to implement?	

Self-Reflection on the training

Item	Description
How accessible was the topic for the participants?	
How did the digital tools perform, e.g., the Projects platform or OpenPlato?	
Were the participants actively engaged?	
Which challenges arose?	
Which improvements do you suggest from your perspective?	
Did any external organisations participate in your session? If yes, please specify which ones.	
General observations, if any	

Documentation of collected feedback from participants

Item	Description
Please use the provided miro board link and let participants complete the board – preferably take a screenshot.	

Alternatively: Make photos of flip-chart paper and transcribe written results.	
Please comment on the results - How can you explain this evaluation result?	
Was the training evaluated within your institution? If yes, please briefly provide results.	

Thank you!

13 Appendix E: Guideline for interviews with programme chairs, training facilitators, and coordinators

Question	Intention of the question
<p>To start, could you please describe your role and how you are connected to the PATTERN project?</p> <p>Can you summarise the PATTERN training activities in which your institution was involved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>It's not necessary to provide a list of activities, we are just interested in the main aspects from your perspective.</i> <p>How were these PATTERN trainings integrated into the curricula or programmes at your institution?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>E.g. were the trainings extracurricular, implemented in existing courses, ...</i> 	<p>Interviewee's summary/overview with PATTERN trainings</p>
<p>What were your motivations for implementing the PATTERN trainings at your institution?</p> <p>Which outcomes of implementing the PATTERN trainings could you observe?</p> <p>How did PATTERN influence the political climate or social norms at your institution?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E.g., where there changes in policies, funding, support, attitudes towards Open Science and RRI? <p>What were barriers and challenges to implementing the PATTERN trainings (if any)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were barriers related to the researchers, as training participants? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ <i>E.g., limited interest, difficulties in promoting trainings</i> • What were barriers related to resources for implementation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ <i>Resources such as budget or time</i> 	<p>Interviewee's assessment of the PATTERN trainings</p>

Question	Intention of the question
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were barriers related to administration, management, or bureaucracy? • What were barriers related to the political climate or social norms at your institution? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ <i>E.g., barriers related to reduced funding, regulations, policies, negative attitudes towards Open Science and RRI?</i> <p>Which other trainings related to Open Science and RRI have you implemented at your institution before (if any)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>If other trainings have been implemented:</i> • How are these trainings similar to the PATTERN trainings? • How are these trainings different from the PATTERN trainings? • How were these other trainings received by the trainees/training participants? 	
<p>Will your institution continue to use the PATTERN platforms (OpenPlato and Projects) after the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes: how? • If no: why not? <p>Will your institution continue to implement the PATTERN trainings or other Open Science trainings after the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes: how? • If no: why not? <p>To which extent did you get access to new networks or partnerships because of PATTERN? Can you provide any relevant examples?</p> <p>To which extent did you get access to new infrastructure because of PATTERN? Can you provide any relevant examples?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>E.g. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)</i> 	<p>Sustainability of trainings and training infrastructure</p>

Question	Intention of the question
<p>To which extent did you get access to new funding opportunities or partnerships because of PATTERN? Can you provide any relevant examples?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>E.g. Erasmus+ ...</i> 	
<p>In your opinion, are the PATTERN trainings a good way for universities to address the topics of Open Science and RRI?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If yes, why? And in what way? • If not, why? • How could PATTERN trainings contribute to universities' third mission goals? 	Impact on Open Science & RRI
<p>Imagine the project were extended for another five years — what would you still wish for, or what would you like to see more of?</p> <p>How do you think an extended timeline could enhance the project's overall impact?</p>	

14 Appendix F: Guidelines for translation

All materials provided by the ZSI teams are in English. If you want to translate the materials for training participants to a different language, you can follow the guidelines outlined below.

14.1.1 Participant Questionnaire

Standardised questionnaires such as the online questionnaire for participants (see 4.3) should be translated carefully and systematically. Since the questionnaires are supposed to be standardised to enable comparison of responses across different groups, it's important to stick as closely as possible to the original meaning.

We have outlined best practices for the translations of standardised or quantitative questionnaires below. We are aware that translation can be a tedious and effortful process and advise you to adapt the process to your own resources.

The TRAPD method is considered best practice for questionnaire translation (see e.g. Walde & Völlm, 2023 or <https://europeanvaluesstudy.eu/methodology-data-documentation/survey-2017/methodology/the-trapd-method-for-survey-translation/>). It consists of several steps:

- Translation: a questionnaire is translated by at least two independent translators;
- Review: the translators and an additional reviewer compare the translations and decide on one translation;
- Adjudication: the reviewer compares the reviewed translation with the master questionnaire (i.e., the original);
- Pretest: the approved translation is pretested in the field and revised based on the pre-tests;
- Documentation: the whole process and the final translation is documented.

Forward-Back translation is another approach very often used in questionnaire translation, whereby a questionnaire is translated into the target language, then translated back into the original language by different translators, and both versions are compared to increase accuracy. Cheung et al. (2020) report on such a translation process consisting of 5 steps:

1. Recruiting a balanced translation team including people familiar with the topic and content of the questionnaire (e.g., familiar with concepts of trainings in high education) and familiar with the target language (i.e., native speaker or qualified translator). Cheung et al. (2020) recommend to recruit at least four translators with different skills who are grouped into balanced pairs.
2. Forward translation, assuming the translation team consists of 2 pairs: the first pair creates a forward translation, translating the original questionnaire into the target language. This translation is discussed with a fifth person acting as reviewer and revised if necessary.
3. Back-translation: the second pair of translators use the translated questionnaire and translates it back to the original language. The two

versions of the questionnaire in the original language are compared to highlight potential misunderstandings or inaccuracies.

4. Consolidation: the entire team of translators examines and revises the translation based on the different versions of the questionnaire. They then agree on a single translation.
5. Pilot testing and finalising: the questionnaire agreed upon in the previous step is pilot tested with 10 to 40 participants who provide feedback. This provides the basis for a final revision and finalisation of the translated questionnaire.

Notably, these best practice procedures take a lot of effort and time. There are simpler methods of translation, which might reduce the questionnaire's validity in favour of using less resources.

Recently, researchers have proposed a forward-back translation process using machine-generated translations which were of similar quality to human-generated translations (Kunst & Bierwiazzonek, 2023). This is especially effective with languages that share the same language family. Such a machine-supported translation process may include the following steps:

- Forward translation: The questionnaire is translated into the target language using one machine translation app (e.g., DeepL).
- Back-translation: the translated questionnaire is translated back to its original language by a different machine translation app which is based on a different language model.
- A bilingual researcher compares and adjusts the translations, resulting in a final translated questionnaire. If possible, these comparisons and adjustments should be done in a team through joint discussions.

After you have decided on a translation procedure, we ask you to use the template below to document the final translation you use for the questionnaire and share it with the ZSI team.

Target Language of the Translation:		
	English Original	Translation
Introductory text	<p>Thank you for participating in the PATTERN training!</p> <p>We would like to ask you some questions about your training experience. Completing the questionnaire will take approximately 5 minutes.</p> <p>Your honest feedback allows us to improve and refine our trainings.</p> <p>All your answers are anonymous and cannot be traced to you. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time. No personal identifying information will be collected and collected data will be treated in compliance with the GDPR. Your responses will be kept confidential. Aggregated responses will solely be used for research purposes and improvements of the training. By proceeding, you consent to participate in this survey. Thank you for your time.</p> <p>Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements about your training experience.</p>	
Response Scale	Strongly disagree	
	Disagree	

Target Language of the Translation:		
	English Original	Translation
	Somewhat disagree	
	Neither agree nor disagree	
	Somewhat agree	
	Agree	
	Strongly agree	
	Not applicable	
Item 1	The training materials were clear.	
Item 2	The training materials were relevant and up to date.	
Item 3	It seemed to me that the training tried to cover too many topics.	
Item 4	The training taught me a lot of new concepts.	
Item 5	I managed to complete the requirements of the training without feeling unduly stressed.	
Item 6	The training provided sufficient flexibility for my personal learning needs.	
Item 7	The training was well structured.	
Item 8	I was given the chance to actively engage during the training.	

Target Language of the Translation:		
	English Original	Translation
Item 9	The aims and objectives of this training were NOT made very clear.	
Item 10	The online platforms used in the training were adequate tools for learning.	
Item 11	During the training, my interest in the topic was increased.	
Item 12	Overall, the training experience was worthwhile.	
Item 13	Overall, I'm satisfied with the quality of this training.	
Age	What is your age? (in years)	
Gender	What is your gender?	
	Male	
	Female	
	Non-binary	
	Prefer not to say	
	Other: [open field]	
Discipline	What is your primary academic discipline or field of study?	
	Arts & Humanities (e.g., Literature, Philosophy)	
	Social Sciences (e.g., Sociology, Psychology)	
	Natural Sciences (e.g., Biology, Chemistry)	
	Engineering & Technology (e.g., Computer Science, Engineering)	
	Medical & Health Sciences (e.g., Medicine, Nursing)	
	Business & Economics (e.g., Business Administration, Economics)	
	Other: [open field]	
Career Stage	What best describes your current academic or professional stage?	

Target Language of the Translation:		
	English Original	Translation
	Bachelor's student	
	Master's student	
	Doctoral student or predoctoral researcher	
	Postdoctoral researcher	
	Senior scientist or Professor	

Table 2. Translation template for participant questionnaire.

14.1.2 Interactive Evaluation Activity

The interactive evaluation activity (see 4.4) consists of quantitative and qualitative questions. We suggest using the same translation procedure as for the online questionnaire.

Please use the template below to document the final translation you use for the activity and share it with the ZSI team.

Target Language of the Translation:		
	English Original	Translation
Instruction text (left-hand side)	Rate the statements by dragging the post its along the line. Write comments and thoughts on the post-it you dragged.	
Item text	The training I participated in, I rate as follows ...	
Item 1	I enjoyed the training - because of ...	
Item 2	The training was useful for me - and why ...	
Item 3	I could gain new skills - and which ...	
Item 4	I will apply what I have learned in practice - what in specific ...	
Response Scale	Fully disagree	
Instruction text (right-hand side)	Please provide general feedback and ideas for improving the training using the post-its.	
Item text	My ideas for improvement are ...	

Table 3. Translation template for Interactive Evaluation Activity.

15 Appendix G: Additional statistical results

15.1 Response frequencies for each participant questionnaire item

15.2 Detailed results for group comparisons - Discipline

15.3 Detailed results for group comparisons - Career

15.4 Detailed results for group comparisons - Gender

$F_{\text{Welch}}(3, 25.6) = 7.29, p = 1.09e-03, \hat{\omega}_p^2 = 0.39, CI_{95\%} [0.10, 1.00], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,677$

The online platforms used in the training were adequate tools for learning.

$$F_{\text{Welch}}(3, 20.97) = 3.28, p = 0.04, \hat{\omega}_p^2 = 0.22, CI_{95\%} [0.00, 1.00], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,573$$

During the training, my interest in the topic was increased.

$$F_{\text{Welch}}(3, 25.15) = 6.69, p = 1.80e-03, \hat{\omega}_p^2 = 0.37, CI_{95\%} [0.08, 1.00], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,677$$

15.5 Detailed results for group comparisons – Thematic Area

15.6 Detailed results for group comparisons – Training Format

The aims and objectives of this training were NOT made very clear.

The online platforms used in the training were adequate tools for learning

15.7 Detailed results for group comparisons – Projects Platform

$t_{\text{Welch}}(1111.7) = 5.66, p = 1.97\text{e-}08, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.29, \text{CI}_{95\%} [0.19, 0.39], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,743$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(1280.97) = 2.15, p = 0.03, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.11, \text{CI}_{95\%} [9.31\text{e-}03, 0.21], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,741$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(1342.66) = 1.62, p = 0.11, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.08, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.02, 0.18], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,746$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(1500.05) = -5.25, p = 1.73\text{e-}07, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.25, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.35, -0.16], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,737$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(1162.59) = 4.03, p = 6.01e-05, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.20, CI_{95\%} [0.10, 0.30], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,743$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(1109.24) = 5.26, p = 1.72e-07, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.27, CI_{95\%} [0.17, 0.37], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,746$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(1239.44) = 3.62, p = 3.12\text{e-}04, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.18, \text{CI}_{95\%} [0.08, 0.28], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,746$

15.8 Detailed results for group comparisons – OpenPlato Platform

$t_{\text{Welch}}(176.99) = -2.60, p = 0.01, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.22, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.39, -0.05], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,735$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(167.38) = -0.64, p = 0.52, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.06, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.24, 0.12], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,733$

aged to complete the requirements of the training without feeling unduly st

$$t_{\text{Welch}}(169.93) = 0.39, p = 0.69, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.04, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.14, 0.21], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,698$$

The training provided sufficient flexibility for my personal learning needs.

$$t_{\text{Welch}}(173.02) = -2.19, p = 0.03, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.19, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.36, -0.02], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,715$$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(178.03) = -2.11, p = 0.04, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.18, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.35, -0.01], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,738$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(207.94) = -2.89, p = 4.21\text{e-}03, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.21, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.35, -0.07], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,729$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(186.33) = -2.83, p = 5.11e-03, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.23, CI_{95\%} [-0.39, -0.07], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,735$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(196.41) = -4.90, p = 2.01e-06, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.37, CI_{95\%} [-0.53, -0.22], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,738$

$t_{\text{Welch}}(180.35) = -3.23, p = 1.46\text{e-}03, \hat{g}_{\text{Hedges}} = -0.27, \text{CI}_{95\%} [-0.44, -0.10], n_{\text{obs}} = 1,738$

15.9 Additional graphs from network analysis

Node Strength

Communities of Nodes

Node strength

Communities of Nodes

PATTERN.

Empowering Open and Responsible
Research and Innovation

OUR CONSORTIUM

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